

**Valuing the Contributions of National
Earth and Environmental Science
Facilities Forum Members:
Pilot Impact Assessment**

A Lateral Economics Report for the
National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities
Forum

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Glossary

ABS	Australian Bureau of Statistics
AI	Artificial intelligence
ACCESS	Australian Community Climate & Earth System Simulator
ALTAR	Australian Long-Term Agroecosystem Research Network
AODN	Australian Open Data Network
APPN	Australian Plant Phenomics Network
BCR	Benefit-cost ratio
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CoastRI	Coastal Research Infrastructure
CV	Contingent valuation
E&E	Earth and Environment
EMSA	Ecological Monitoring System Australia (EMSA)
EO	Earth observation
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
GA	Geoscience Australia
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GBOV	Ground-Based Observations for Validation
GBR	Great Barrier Reef
GRDC	Grains Research and Development Corporation
HPC	High Performance Computing/Computer
ILTER	International Long-Term Ecological Research Network
IMOS	Integrated Marine Observing System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LHC	Large Hadron Collider

LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MNF	Marine National Facility
NCRIS	National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy
NEESFF	National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities Forum
NPV	Net Present Value
NRM	Natural Resource Management
NSF	National Science Foundation
OPEX	Operating expenses
PHRN	Population Health Research Network
PV	Present Value
RIIP	Research Infrastructure Investment Plans
RoI	Return on Investment
SARDI	South Australian Research and Development Institute
SCRVF	Southern Coastal Research Vessel Fleet
SeaSim	National Sea Simulator
TERN	Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WGCV	Working Group on Calibration and Validation
WTP	Willingness to Pay

Executive Summary

This report presents the results of Lateral Economics' (LE's) pilot impact assessment of the National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities Forum (NEESFF). The Forum brings together Australia's leading earth and environmental science research infrastructure facilities with the aim of ensuring that national investments deliver maximum scientific, economic, and societal value.

This study is only a pilot impact assessment because NEESFF encompasses such a diverse range of organisations that it is impossible to fully capture and assess all its impacts without undertaking a wider and more extensive program of work than scoped out for this project. As part of the project, LE consulted with all NEESFF organisations (see Appendix A), and obtained insights into the benefits offered by each of them. However, it was not possible within the scope of work to undertake quantification of benefits and costs for all organisations. Instead, we focussed on three case studies from three different organisations.

We applied a cost–benefit analysis (CBA) framework to evaluate the contributions of selected facilities. The three case studies were of the:

- Atlas of Living Australia (ALA);
- Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN); and the
- Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN).

This allowed for a systematic comparison of the costs of infrastructure provision against the broad range of benefits these facilities generate. These benefits include scientific outputs, support for industry innovation, environmental management improvements, and contributions to national resilience in the face of climate, natural hazard, and resource challenges.

A CBA is essential to evaluate the case for public investment in NEESFF organisations. Individual NEESFF organisations capture excellent metrics around user uptake, science impact through publication tracking systems, and user satisfaction through surveys, but lack the capability to evaluate economic benefits to support their conversations with co-investors, project partners and governments.

We have combined the results of three new case studies of NEESFF organisations with the results of previous studies to estimate **an average benefit-cost ratio (BCR) for NEESFF organisations of 6.8** (Table A). Using this average BCR and based on estimated total NEESFF annual public funding of \$235 million, we estimate that **total annual NEESFF benefits exceed \$1.5 billion**.

Table A. Benefit-cost ratios for NEESFF organisations

Organisation	Benefit-cost ratio (Central case)	Source
<i>Existing studies</i>		
AAF	8.5	Lateral Economics (2025)
ALA	3.5	Alluvium (2016)
AuScope	15.0	Lateral Economics (2016)
IMOS	4.7	Lateral Economics (2021)
MNF	4.7	RTI International (2020)
<i>New case studies</i>		
ALA	3.8	Case study conducted for this report
APPN	6.7	As above
TERN	7.0	As above
Weighted average across all studies*	6.8	

* Note: The weighted average is calculated by weighting the benefit-cost ratios in Table A by Australian Government funding provided to the organisations since 2017-18. The LE estimated benefit-cost ratio for ALA is used rather than Alluvium's 2016 estimate.

Fiscal return to the Australian Government

With such a high benefit-cost ratio across NEESFF organisations—and assuming the average we calculate is representative of all NEESFF organisations—we expect a significant fiscal return to taxpayers of investment in NEESFF. Even if only half of the benefits entering into the average BCR of 6.8 contributed to higher GDP, assuming a 30% average tax share of GDP based on Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) data, that would mean \$1.02 of every dollar paid out is returned in taxation revenue. That is, NEESFF may well pay for itself through higher tax revenue, even before counting the benefits our analysis suggests accrue to the community more widely.

Next steps

The next steps in this project include revising this report following any feedback from NEESFF organisations and supplementing this pilot impact assessment with the following:

- **Standardised data collection instruments and protocols** to support consistent, reliable, and comparable data gathering across NEESFF member organisations.
- **An interactive impact dashboard/scorecard** to summarily (where possible visually) communicate key project findings and support ongoing advocacy and strategic decision-making by NEESFF stakeholders.

- The dashboard would include a mix of input and output indicators and benefit and cost estimates—e.g. benefit-cost ratio and internal-rate-of-return benefit estimates, and relevant indicators that inform the calculation of benefits (e.g. scientific publications, indicators of research inputs used or data collected, etc.), and capital and operational expenditures.
- The goal is that the dashboard would show a clear link between NEESFF inputs, activities, outputs and the net benefit estimates.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope of work

The National Earth and Environmental Science Facilities Forum (NEESFF) has commissioned Lateral Economics to assess the value of NEESFF to the Australian community. Historically, individual NCRIS-funded facilities within NEESFF have commissioned specific assessments to quantify and demonstrate their value, notably through cost-benefit analyses (CBAs) and return-on-investment (ROI) studies. Examples include successful evaluations completed by Lateral Economics for AuScope, the Australian Access Federation (AAF), and IMOS, alongside a comprehensive, whole-of-NCRIS assessment conducted in 2021.

These evaluations have strengthened the evidence about the economic and social value these investments have generated. This has made the evaluations highly valuable for advocacy, policy justification, and strategic communication at both national and international levels. Indeed, the ROI analysis undertaken for IMOS, in particular, has served as a benchmark in various global forums, vividly illustrating the tangible benefits delivered through marine data infrastructure.

Recognising this success, the NEESFF has identified a need to extend this approach across its broader membership. The overarching goal is to produce a similarly compelling evaluation framework capable of demonstrating the collective impact of these diverse yet interconnected capabilities. Specifically, NEESFF seeks to develop an analytical method—whether through a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis, tailored ROI evaluation, or an alternative approach—capable of systematically quantifying the benefits, economic impacts, scientific contributions, and broader societal outcomes of its collective environmental research infrastructure.

1.2. About NEESFF

1.2.1. Member organisations

NEESFF represents a diverse collective of Australia's foremost environmental research and infrastructure capabilities, mainly funded through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) (Table 1). This group seeks to articulate and quantify the value it collectively contributes to Australia. Some organisations have a range of activities, only some of which fall within the scope of NEESFF. For instance, only a fraction of the computing time expended at NCI or Pawsey relates to earth and environmental sciences research.

Table 1.1. NEESFF organisations participating in the study by the nature of their primary activity

Observational / monitoring	Data/information tools, integration & access	Computation & simulation
Australian Plant Phenomics Network	AAF	ACCESS-NRI
BioPlatforms Australia	ALA	National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)
IMOS	ARDC	Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre
Marine National Facility	AuScope	
Southern Coastal Research Vessel Fleet	AURIN	
TERN		
National Sea Simulator (SeaSim)		

1.2. NEESFF organisations resourcing

NEESFF organisations are resourced through a coordinated network of national research infrastructure, mainly backed by NCRIS.¹ Table 1.2 shows the Australian Government funding, which has totalled \$1.6 billion from 2017-18 to the latest funding round in 2025. This funding is held every 1-2 years and is targeted towards specific National Research Infrastructure (NRI) needs. The organisation receiving the largest amount of public funding was BioPlatforms Australia with \$260.8 million (15.9% of the total funding) since 2017-18, followed by ARDC with \$ 254.1 million (15.5%), and IMOS with \$ 186.4 million (11.4%). At this stage, available information has not allowed us to produce a full financial data set for all NEESFF facilities.

¹ The Australian Government invests in NRI through the NCRIS program, which funds priority projects identified in Roadmaps and occasional emerging needs. NCRIS maximises impact by coordinating open access, fostering co-funding with universities, governments, Publicly Funded Research Agencies (PFRA) and industry, and supporting collaboration across disciplines and borders.

Table 1.2. Commonwealth Government funding by NEESFF organisations (\$ million)

Organisation	NRI Planned Investment 2017–18 to 2021–22 (*)	NCRIS 2020 Research Infrastruc- ture Investme nt Plans (RIIP) (**)	NCRIS 2022 Funding Round 2023-24 to 2027-28	NCRIS 2023 Funding Round	NCRIS 2025 Funding Round
AAF	-	-	-	2.9	-
ALA	2.1	2.4	28.5	3.5	-
ACCESS-NRI	3.2	7.6	17.3	9.6	-
AuScope	1.5	5.7	45.1	45.0	-
AURIN	7.4	5.1	12.9	12.3	-
ARDC (***)	72.2	15.9	119.6	46.5	-
APPN	2.1	1.9	27.0	15.9	-
APPF	2.6	6.1	22.8	37.3	-
BioPlatforms Australia	48.1	14.3	85.4	113.0	-
IMOS	22.0	5.9	95.0	63.5	-
TERN	5.1	5.9	36.7	29.0	-
Marine National Facility	31.2	7.6	33.5	59.3	-
NCI	76.3	-	33.3	-	55.0
Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre	70.0	-	35.1	5.0	22.0
Southern Coastal Research Vessels	-	0.7	4.1	19.0	-
SeaSim	-	36.3	29.8	15.1	-
Total	343.8	115.3	626.1	477.1	77.0

Source: [Department of Education](#), Australian Government.

Notes: (*) The \$3.2 million figure for ACCESS-NRI represents the funding for scoping studies that involve other organisations. (**) National Computational Infrastructure and Pawsey Supercomputing Centre were also funded through NCRIS via the National Innovation and Science Agenda. (***) The ARDC's \$72.2 million comes from the eResearch Project fund allocation. The ARDC was formed in 2018 through the merger of three existing digital research infrastructure facilities: the Australian National Data Service (ANDS), National eResearch Collaboration Tools and Resources (Nectar) and Research Data Services (RDS).

2. Methodological issues

2.1. Frameworks

LE's methodology has been informed by the OECD's Reference Framework for Assessing the Scientific and Socio-Economic Impact of Research Infrastructure and will be informed by relevant economic studies—e.g. the cost-benefit analysis of the Large Hadron Collider.

2.1.1. OECD Reference Framework

The NEESFF impact assessment is intended to be consistent with international best practice by closely aligning with the OECD's Reference Framework for Assessing the Scientific and Socio-Economic Impact of Research Infrastructures.² The Reference Framework acknowledges the challenges of estimating the benefits of research infrastructure facilities (Figure 1) and, hence, recommends a mix of methods.

Figure 1. Challenges in assessing the impacts or benefits of research infrastructures

The Reference Framework recommends a carefully selected set of Core Impact Indicators (CIIs) and supplementary indicators, encompassing scientific outcomes (e.g., publications and citations), innovation impacts (e.g., industry collaborations), educational outreach, support for public policy, economic contributions, and sustainability.

² Source: OECD (2019) Reference Framework for Assessing the Scientific & Socio-economic Impact of Research Infrastructures, STI Policy Paper.

The Reference Framework recommends that consistent and systematic data collection methods be established, leveraging existing administrative data where possible to ensure reliability and reduce costs. Qualitative information, including case studies and targeted surveys, can complement quantitative data to capture nuance, illustrate the concrete outcomes otherwise captured in abstract measures of value and to add clarity and vibrancy to communicating these things internally and to those outside the organisations.

2.1.2. Quantifying ROI

The Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) by Florio et al.³ is an internationally respected benchmark for conducting credible, comprehensive, and robust CBAs, making it highly suitable as a methodological approach for evaluating Australia's national environmental science infrastructure. It systematically categorises benefits into clearly defined groups: scientific outputs, human capital gains, industry spillovers, cultural engagement, and the non-use value of scientific knowledge (Table 2).

Table 2. Benefit estimation of the LHC—a good example of benefit quantification for research infrastructure

Direct beneficiary group	Notes on methods
Scientists	Estimate benefit of papers by non-LHC scientists citing LHC papers, valued at estimated production cost base on average salary and time taken to produce paper.
Students & post-docs	Human capital formation benefit based on earnings premium of LHC students/post-docs in later career.
Firms & other organisations	Technological spillovers estimated as incremental profits of firms in the LHC supply chain in other markets.
General public	On-site visitation benefits estimated using revealed preference/travel cost method.
	Non-use benefit of scientific knowledge as a public good. Contingent valuation study.

Source: Florio, M. et al. (2016) "Forecasting the socio-economic impact of the Large Hadron Collider", Technological Forecasting & Social Change, vol. 112, pp. 38-53.

This structured classification aligns well with NEESFF's diverse infrastructure portfolio, offering a practical framework for capturing and monetising various dimensions of value.

³ Florio, M. et al. (2016) "Forecasting the socio-economic impact of the Large Hadron Collider", Technological Forecasting & Social Change, vol. 112, pp. 38-53.

A key strength of the LHC study is its integration of rigorous quantitative methods—such as scientometric analysis and Monte Carlo risk simulations—with qualitative approaches, including surveys of perceived skills improvement and contingent valuation methods to capture broader societal values. This hybrid approach ensures comprehensiveness, robustness, and transparency, enhancing credibility among stakeholders.

Florio *et al.* further demonstrate meticulous treatment of uncertainty through advanced risk and sensitivity analyses. Assigning probability distributions to critical variables provides insights into potential outcomes and this can inform strategic decision-making. To address uncertainty, the researchers applied a Monte Carlo simulation with 10,000 runs, assigning probability distribution functions to 19 key variables. This allowed them to generate probability distributions for important CBA metrics such as the net present value (NPV), discussed further below. For example, future costs of collaboration with CERN over 2014 to 2025 were modelled as a normal distribution with a mean of €1.97 billion and a $\pm 50\%$ range. Human capital benefits incorporated uncertainty in the number of early-stage researchers ($\pm 15\%$ around the mean) and the estimated salary “premium” from LHC experience. The simulation results indicated a 90% probability that benefits exceed costs.

2.2. Methodological Techniques

In our interviews with NEESFF organisations, we sought to identify the Core Impact Indicators of organisations. Where possible with existing data, this was done with a view to demonstrating how these indicators can be translated into dollar benefit estimates as outlined in greater detail in the following section.

2.2.1. Quantitative Evaluation Techniques

We will use Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), guided by well-established guidelines on CBA in Australia (e.g. from Infrastructure Australia and the Office of Impact Assessment), and also by Florio *et al.*

This involves the identification and attribution of costs, including:

- Capital expenditures (CAPEX);
- Operational expenditures (OPEX);
- Other relevant economic costs, such as deadweight losses from the way in which taxation changes behaviour (Generally accepted estimates of this suggest that around 25c in every dollar of taxation raised is lost in this way).

It also involves the estimation of benefits, including:

- **Use benefits**—e.g. resource discoveries, improved fisheries management, weather forecasting accuracy, or natural disaster preparedness, economic value generated by geospatial data.
- **Non-use benefits**, particularly the existence value (EXV) of scientific knowledge, ideally estimated using contingent valuation techniques (Box 2.1). Non-use benefits can include the quasi-option value (QOV) of future discoveries, such as from the future but unforeseeable economic exploitation of basic research. This non-use benefit is often unmeasured, as in the CBA for the LHC discussed above. A separate consideration is that non-use benefits can be negative - with the genie being unable to be put back in the bottle. Our mastery of nuclear technology comes with major costs in the form of nuclear weapons. And our mastery of genetic engineering creates the prospect of new pathogens.

Box 2.1. Using Contingent Valuation to Estimate the Existence Value of the LHC

Existence value refers to society's willingness-to-pay (WTP) for scientific knowledge independent of any direct or immediate practical use. To estimate this important but intangible component, the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) employed a contingent valuation method. Specifically, a carefully designed survey was conducted, targeting university students across four European countries—Italy, the UK, France, and Spain—who represented future taxpayers. The survey asked respondents how much they would be willing to pay annually for the scientific discoveries arising from LHC research, presenting them with discrete payment options of €0.5, €1, or €2 per year.

More than 1,000 respondents completed a structured questionnaire, designed to clearly and realistically elicit their valuation of scientific research outcomes. To ensure informed responses, each participant was provided with concise background information about the LHC, highlighting its purpose, significant scientific achievements, and potential future discoveries.

The study adopted conservative assumptions, assigning zero WTP to all taxpayers without tertiary education. The existence value was subsequently calculated by aggregating individual responses across the surveyed population, extrapolated over a 30-year period, reflecting society's valuation of the knowledge produced by the LHC.

This contingent valuation approach produced a substantial existence value, estimated at €3.2 billion. Incorporating this figure into the overall CBA underscored the substantial intangible benefits that society attributes to fundamental scientific infrastructure, reinforcing the importance of considering non-use values when assessing large-scale scientific investments.

Benefits and costs are estimated for several years, generally for the lifecycle of the current research infrastructure, which could be up to 20 or 30 years.

The quantification of benefits will be based on data from the facilities and parameters (e.g. dollar value of benefit per research paper) as determined by our literature review or official guidelines (e.g. Office of Impact Assessment guidelines on the value of time saved or a statistical life). Assuming NEESFF organisations are interested in the future net benefits of their current activities, the CBA will estimate the future benefits and costs based on appropriate assumptions.

Once benefit and cost estimates are assembled, they are converted to present values, adjusting for the time value of money. There is a large debate around the appropriate discount

rate by which to do so. The Office of Impact Analysis recommends a central 7% real discount rate (i.e. the discount rate used to generate the headline results), with 3% and 10% rates used for sensitivity.⁴ However, we agree with the Grattan Institute that, given the lower borrowing costs observed in the last decade, a lower discount rate should be used. Grattan recommends a figure between 3.5-5%.⁵ Hence, we will present two 'central case' results using the 7% recommended by PM&C and 4.25% — the mid-point of Grattan's range together with our own recommendation that the second of these two options is a more professionally defensible approach.

The cost-benefit analysis will specify clearly defined decision-making metrics, including:

- Net Present Value (NPV), the value of net benefits in today's dollars, estimated by discounting future values back to the present at the chosen discount rate;
- Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR), the present value of benefits divided by the present value of costs; and
- Internal Rate of Return (IRR), the yield of the program or project—the discount rate at which the NPV would be zero.

These metrics help decision makers evaluate government projects or programs. If a project has a positive NPV or BCR of 1 or more, the metrics are supportive of the project or the program. CBA metrics should not necessarily be the sole determinant of a decision, however, as other considerations may justify projects or programs going ahead or not. These considerations not quantified in the CBA could include equity issues, or other objectives such as cultural values or regional economic development.

To summarise, the CBA involves quantification, using the best available data and assumptions, the benefits and costs related to research infrastructure facilities over time and the calculation of the NPV of the facility. The relevant equations are set out in Box 2.2.

⁴ PM&C (2020) Guidance Note on Cost-Benefit Analysis.

⁵ Terrill, M. and Batrouney, H. (2018) Unfreezing discount rates: Transport infrastructure for tomorrow. Grattan Institute.

Box 2.2. Calculating the NPV of research infrastructure

$$NPV_{RI} = NPV_{use} + B_{non-use}$$

$$= (PV_{use_benefits} - (PV_{capex} + PV_{opex})) + (QOV_{t=0} + EXV_{t=0})$$

NPV = Net Present Value (i.e. net benefits after discounting future values)

PV = Present value ((i.e. current values after discounting)

$B_{non-use}$ = non-use values related to future discoveries

QOV = quasi-option value of future, unpredictable economic benefits of new knowledge (assumed non-negative and set to 0)

EXV = existence value; proxied by willingness to pay (WTP) for new knowledge (estimated by Contingent Valuation survey)

Source: Florio, M. et al. (2016) "Forecasting the socio-economic impact of the Large Hadron Collider", Technological Forecasting & Social Change, vol. 112, pp. 38-53.

2.2.2. Qualitative Evaluation Techniques

Recognising the limitations of purely quantitative methods, qualitative techniques can supplement our understanding of broader societal and indirect impacts. We have interviewed all NEESFF organisations to gain an understanding of both quantitative and qualitative benefits. Organisations interviewed are listed in Appendix A and the template of questions we used in the interviews is included in Appendix B. The insights we gained from the interviews and from desktop research are presented in Section 3 which follows.

3. Key insights into NEESFF organisations

3.1. Consistent themes

Consultations with NEESFF organisations, supplemented by desktop research revealed several consistent themes across organisations:

1. **Difficulty in quantifying benefits.** Many organisations, especially newer ones like ACCESS-NRI, find it challenging to quantify their economic and social benefits due to their being in their early stages or the diffuse nature of their impact. Other challenges include:

- a. Significant benefits are realised internationally (e.g. IMOS contributes to global ocean monitoring), and this is challenging to evaluate from both research impact and economic perspectives.
 - b. Research impacts can be long-term and difficult to judge in advance and attempt to quantify in dollar terms.
2. **Market failure and unique capabilities.** Several organisations, including Pawsey, highlighted that their work addresses market failures (Box 3.1) and offers unique, essential capabilities not available commercially.
3. **Underpinning infrastructure.** Many NEESFF organisations act as crucial underpinning infrastructure, enabling other research, industries, and government functions. Their value is manifested through facilitating seamless access, data sharing, and reducing duplication (e.g. AAF, AURIN, TERN, etc.).
4. **Collaboration and interconnectedness.** There is a strong emphasis on collaboration and interconnectedness among NEESFF and other NCRIS organisations, fostering new research projects and knowledge and addressing gaps in data or services for researchers.
5. **Data as a key asset.** Aggregated and curated data were consistently highlighted as a significant and enduring asset, growing in value through time - for the research community, government, and industry.
6. **Training and skill development.** Many facilities contribute to training new generations of scientists and building capabilities in universities.

Box 3.1. Market failure

Market failures occur when markets do not allocate resources efficiently or fairly, resulting in outcomes that are suboptimal for society.

A key example is **public goods**, which are non-excludable and non-rivalrous, such as clean air or national defence. Because private actors cannot capture enough of the benefits, these goods are typically underprovided. Public goods offer a specific example of a wider phenomenon which often drives market failure: Externalities.

Externalities are present wherever the costs or benefits of an activity spill over to others without being reflected in prices. Pollution is a negative externality, while scientific and industrial research and development (R&D) often generate positive spillovers.

Markets can fail due to **information asymmetry**, where buyers or sellers lack sufficient knowledge to make good decisions and so have incentives to take advantage of the

ignorance of those they trade with, as in cases of hidden product risks or misleading terms on a contract.

Market power is another source of inefficiency, with monopolies or cartels restricting output and raising prices at the expense of their customers.

Finally, **coordination failures** arise when individuals or firms do not act because they are waiting for others to do so, which is common in infrastructure investment or the adoption of new technologies.

These forms of market failure can justify collective responses—through policy, regulation, or other institutions—to ensure more efficient, equitable, and/or sustainable outcomes.

Box 3.2 Collective needs and collective purpose: An under-theorised aspect of market failure

A recurring feature of NCRIS and NEESFF facilities is the presence of large fixed investments that cannot be met by individual users but are indispensable across fields. For instance the Marine National Facility's research vessel discussed below represents a multi-million-dollar capital asset that dozens of research groups benefit from. But the demand of each of them on its own takes up a small fraction of its capacity. In this context, demand is too fragmented, too lumpy, and too uncertain to generate an investable proposition for a profit seeking entrepreneur.

It follows that these facilities are provided in the way they are (they are generally governed by academic stakeholders and funded by governments) to overcome a kind of 'market failure'. The principle market failures that have been theorised by economists include:

- public good characteristics (non-rivalrousness and non-excludability)
- externalities
- monopoly
- information asymmetries

However, this does not describe the kind of market failure to be overcome here. Markets coordinate in an indirect way. Everyone seeks their own interest, and as the market 'deepens' - with more buyers and sellers entering the market - it serves all their needs in a remarkable, some might say 'miraculous', way. But as Hayek put it, while the market serves the private purposes of those trading within it, by its nature, it is *itself*, purposeless.⁶

By contrast the entities in NCRIS/NEESFF *have been brought into and are maintained in existence by the collective purpose of their stakeholders*. Cooperative structures—consortia, mutuals, or publicly supported facilities—arise precisely because they can focus the collective intention of many actors in a way that is very difficult to accomplish within markets. They provide a vehicle for pooling risk and internalising benefits, which can accelerate the collective provision of resources that might otherwise never emerge.

Recognising this helps clarify the 'market failure' argument for NEESFF facilities. Such facilities exemplify an institutional logic economists have often neglected: the cooperative creation of shared infrastructure with high fixed costs, broadly distributed benefits, and the provision and governance of which requires more deliberate coordination than markets alone can provide.

3.2. Insights from each NEESFF organisation

⁶ Hayek, 1982. *Law, Legislation and Liberty: A New Statement of the Liberal Principles of Justice and Political Economy*, Routledge Classics, London and New York, p. 38.

3.2.1. ACCESS-NRI

Core Role

The Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator National Research Infrastructure (ACCESS-NRI) is Australia's dedicated national facility for the ACCESS coupled modelling system, which integrates atmosphere, ocean, sea-ice, land surface, atmospheric chemistry, and biogeochemistry modules. As a National Research Infrastructure established under the NCRIS program, ACCESS-NRI supports the development, evaluation, and operation of ACCESS for simulations of past, present, and future climate and weather, across timescales from hours to decades. The model underpins Australia's capacity for credible climate projections, seasonal and regional weather forecasting, risk assessment, and adaptation planning, thus serving the needs of government, industry, and the research community.

Uniqueness and Strategic Value

ACCESS is the largest coupled modelling system developed in the Southern Hemisphere. Its distinctiveness lies in incorporating uniquely Australian elements — such as a specialised land surface model and world-leading Southern Ocean modelling — which allow it to capture critical Earth system processes in our region. This ensures that issues like Antarctic climate dynamics, the confluence of three major ocean basins, and the maritime continent's influence on northern Australian weather are properly prioritised, whereas these are often overlooked in Northern Hemisphere models.

Box 3.3. Coupled modelling systems

A coupled modelling system refers to a computer modelling framework that integrates several component models (e.g. atmosphere, ocean, land surface, sea-ice, biogeochemistry, aerosols) and allows them to exchange information during simulation so as to capture feedback between the components.

For example, ACCESS-CM (ACCESS Coupled Model) includes atmosphere, ocean and sea-ice modules, and is used to simulate physical climate processes.⁷ Meanwhile ACCESS-ESM (The ACCESS Earth System Model) adds further complexity, incorporating biogeochemical cycles (carbon, nutrient cycles, etc.) on land and in ocean, as well as atmospheric chemistry and aerosol interactions.⁸ Such coupled systems allow simulation of climate behaviour over multiple timescales (from seasons to centuries), and under different scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions or land-use change.⁹

Benefits of a Homegrown Model

By developing its own model, Australia ensures it can service, adapt, and improve climate projections for national needs. ACCESS supports practical applications such as carbon cycle modelling, which is essential for evaluating carbon credit claims and assessing progress toward net-zero emissions. Its robustness is demonstrated by the fact that state governments and the Bureau of Meteorology regularly choose ACCESS outputs for downscaled regional modelling, confirming its quality relative to other global models.

Accessibility and Collaboration

ACCESS-NRI makes its model openly available wherever possible, with millions of lines of code (primarily in Fortran) released on GitHub and operable through the National Computational Infrastructure. Researchers can modify parameters, experiment with system components, or change resolution to explore climate processes. This open-source approach both builds Australian expertise and contributes improvements to international partners, creating global knowledge spillovers.

There are prominent examples worldwide of how an open-source approach to modelling produces benefits, including the CICE Consortium Model For Sea-Ice Development, for example.¹⁰ The CICE Consortium model has achieved notable successes, including wide international adoption in both research and operational forecasting, significant improvements in

⁷ <https://www.access-nri.org.au/models/access-cm/>

⁸ <https://github.com/ACCESS-NRI/ACCESS-ESM1.5/blob/main/README.md>

⁹ <https://www.csiro.au/en/research/environmental-impacts/climate-change/ACCESS?>

¹⁰ https://e3sm.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/ResearchHighlight_CICE.pdf

sea ice simulation accuracy, and demonstrated impact in climate system modelling and prediction. Nicholas Gruen [has proposed](#) the same for economic forecasting.

Training and Capability Building

Beyond research, ACCESS-NRI plays a critical role in workforce development. Its annual workshops attract hundreds of participants, including postgraduate students and postdoctoral researchers, while its public forum supports around 500 active users. These activities strengthen national expertise in climate science and computational modelling.

Governance and Partnerships

ACCESS-NRI maintains the technical integrity of the model, ensuring it remains usable and compatible with future supercomputers. Governance follows distributed open-source principles, with contributors retaining veto rights over code changes. The organisation works closely with CSIRO, the Bureau of Meteorology, and international partners such as the UK Met Office and US ocean modelling groups. ACCESS-NRI is working with CSIRO to create Australia's next submission to the World Climate Research Program's Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), which compiles the next generation of climate projections from leading nations.

Challenges and Future Potential

With an asset like ACCESS-NRI, it will always be difficult to fully quantify the value of its outputs. But this is particularly so given that it was established just three years ago. Many new model developments have not yet led to publications or citations. Nevertheless, its role as a provider of public-good infrastructure is expected to yield a high return on investment over time, underpinning climate science, policy development, and adaptation strategies across Australia.

3.2.2. AURIN

Core Role

The Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network (AURIN) provides a national platform for accessing, integrating, and analysing data on Australia's urban centres. It serves around 25,000 users, the majority of whom are students using it as part of their training, alongside thousands of professional researchers and policymakers.¹¹ AURIN hosts over 5,000 datasets, many of which would otherwise be prohibitively expensive or difficult to obtain, such as telecommunications mobility data and sensitive health records.

Data Access and Economic Value

AURIN reduces the transaction costs of research by providing "hard-to-get" datasets. For example, Optus mobility data, which costs \$500,000 annually, has been secured by AURIN for around \$300,000, and then made accessible to researchers. This model enables public-good

¹¹ <https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/introducing-the-spatial-urban-data-observatory/>

benefits while also generating revenue streams through royalties from commercial applications, for instance by property developers. An existing ACIL Allen study has already quantified AURIN's benefits, providing robust evidence of its economic and social value.¹²

Innovation and Applications

AURIN supports new digital tools and analytical platforms. The Housing Analytics Lab (HAL), launched with UNSW City Futures and the NSW Premier, will provide dashboards of planning approvals and AI-based classifiers of planning assessments. These tools will help researchers, planners, and policymakers understand patterns of housing development and potentially enable commercial applications.¹³

The AusEnHealth platform, supported by \$1.9 million in Medical Research Future Fund investment, is being developed as an “environmental health digital twin”. It will integrate climate, air pollution, and health data (e.g. mosquito-borne disease risks), helping policymakers and the public better understand vulnerabilities to heat, extreme weather, and social inequalities.¹⁴

Collaboration and Future Directions

AURIN is increasingly part of a broader digital ecosystem, including the Digital Nexus Alliance with ARDC, NCI, Pawsey, AAF, and AARNet.¹⁵ It is also developing new proposed streams:

- Australian Urban Climate Research Initiative (AUCRI) – a research institute focused on climate change impacts on cities, working with ACCESS-NRI, TERN, PHRN, and ARDC.
- AUMRI – focused on urban mobility, EV adoption, and heavy transport, in collaboration with the ARRB National Transport Research Organisation.
- The Coastal Research Infrastructure (CoastRI) – focused on coastal ecosystems and urban-environmental interactions, with ARDC providing data spaces.

Strategic Importance

By reducing barriers to accessing sensitive, fragmented, and costly datasets, AURIN strengthens Australia's evidence base for urban planning, housing, health, and environmental policy. It plays both a public-good role in supporting research and education, and a commercial role in enabling industry users to save costs and innovate. In this way, AURIN exemplifies

¹² ACIL Allen (2021) Economic contribution of AURIN. Stage 1 Revised Final Report. Report to the Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network. 30 July 2021.

¹³

<https://www.unsw.edu.au/newsroom/news/2025/05/world-leading-unsw-analytics-lab-opens-to-tackle-housing-crisis>

¹⁴ <https://aurin.org.au/1-9-million-in-funding-for-the-ausenhealth-platform/>

¹⁵

https://www.theglobalresearchplatform.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/HOWARD-SCAsia2025-Mini-GRP_SCA25-APRP-SKA-Genomics.pdf

NEESFF facilities' ability to address market failures in data provision (e.g., making expensive private datasets accessible to the public research community) while amplifying national research capability.

3.2.3. AuScope

Core role

AuScope is Australia's national geoscience research infrastructure and is partly NCRIS-funded. It provides the "downward-looking telescope" that lets researchers and decision-makers characterise the continent from surface to core. It delivers tools, datasets and platforms that support work on climate, natural resources security and natural hazards.

What AuScope provides (infrastructure and platforms)

- **Data platforms and standards:** The AuScope Grid/Discovery Portal exposes interoperable geoscience data services and has contributed to international standards like GeosciML—lowering search and integration costs across surveys, universities and industry.
- **Specialised national assets:** The National Virtual Core Library (NVCL)—the world's largest online drill-core mineralogical database—provides over 1.6 million metres of scanned core and tools/training to use it.
- **Positioning and geodesy backbone:** AuScope's geospatial infrastructure (e.g., VLBI antennas, CORS, gravimetry) underpins Australia's dynamic datum and high-precision location for spatially sensitive industries.
- **Compute and software:** Dedicated clusters (e.g., TerraWulf) and open tools (e.g., GPlates, Underworld, ESyS/Esript) enable large-scale modelling, inversion and visualisation.

Economic impact

Lateral Economics' cost-benefit study (2007–14 programs, with benefits projected to 2040–41) found \$3.9 billion gross benefits against \$261 million costs—\$3.6 billion net benefits, a headline BCR of around 15:1. Benefits are concentrated in spatially-sensitive industries (\$2.5 billion, 63% as percentage of gross benefit) and resource exploration (\$0.9 billion, 23%), with additional gains in the natural & built environment (\$0.4 billion, 12%) and existence value of fundamental Earth science.¹⁶

¹⁶

<http://static1.squarespace.com/static/5b440dc18ab722131f76b631/t/5c16d448b8a0454b6add9583/1545000021852/AuScope+Evaluation+of+Impacts+Lateral+Economics+2016.pdf>

Where the value shows up

Exploration productivity & discoveries: Open data, NVCL and modelling tools reduce exploration costs and bring discoveries forward—capturing both cost savings and earlier value-added in minerals and energy.

Economy-wide positioning gains: More accurate, robust positioning raises efficiency in agriculture, transport, mining, construction/surveying and utilities—AuScope’s single largest benefit stream (\$787 million from the grains industry; \$669 million from road transport; \$483 million from mining; \$272 million from construction including land management and surveying; \$167 million from dairy and beef)¹⁷

Risk, planning and environment: Geodesy and Earth imaging enhance hazard assessment, boundary regulation, and land-water planning—public-good benefits that are diffuse yet material.

Training, outreach and pipelines: AuScope supports workforce development through research use of its platforms and through AuSIS (Australian Seismometers in Schools)—deploying research-grade seismometers and educational activities that build STEM capability while generating usable seismic data.

Why public investment is warranted

Geoscience infrastructure exhibits classic market failures: high fixed costs (See Box 3.1), uncertain/long-lived, non-rival knowledge spillovers, and standardisation externalities. AuScope’s interoperable data, national assets (NVCL, geodesy) and enabling software/computing create option value and positive externalities across industries. The measured benefit-cost ratio of 15:1 from the Lateral Economics’ cost–benefit study quantifies only part of that value; long-horizon spillovers and reuse will keep compounding beyond the evaluation window.

3.2.4. Australian Access Federation (AAF)

Core Role

Established in 2009, the Australian Access Federation (AAF) provides a trusted, national identity and access framework for Australia’s research and education sector. It connects almost all Australian universities, major research agencies, NCRIS facilities, government organisations, and international federations (via eduGAIN), enabling secure, seamless access

¹⁷

https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5b440dc18ab722131f76b631/t/5c16d448b8a0454b6add9583/1545000021852/AuScope+Evaluation+of+Impacts_Lateral+Economics+2016.pdf

to digital networks and resources for both research, collaboration and learning. The majority of AAF's funding (66%) is sourced from its subscribers.

Scale

The AAF is part of a global network of over 80 federations. This growth has made the AAF a critical enabler of secure, seamless access to global online resources, with the number of authentications it facilitates increasing significantly over time. In 2025, it supported over 13 million authentications.

AAF provides trusted and seamless interconnectivity for collaborative work both nationally and internationally, fostering a robust framework for authentication and authorisation across organisational boundaries. Stakeholders often take for granted the significant level of trust in AAF, as it effectively “just works” to ensure immediate compliance. By acting as a trusted third-party provider, AAF elevates the digital Trust and Identity (T&I) maturity of distributed research organisations to a common, global standard. Additionally, according to TERN, its utilisation of AAF for sign-on enhances its CoreTrustSeal Certification, further bolstering its reputation as a reliable repository.

Economic and Strategic Value

AAF maximises the value of government investment by minimising duplication, as facilities do not need to build their own costly authentication systems, and ensures that enhancements developed for one partner can be scaled across the sector. This shared national service creates efficiencies, supports interoperability, and fosters interdisciplinary research. Importantly, AAF also aligns Australia with international standards through EduGAIN, preventing the country from becoming an “identity island” and maintaining its capacity to participate in global collaborations such as European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN, an acronym in French) and National Science Foundation (NSF) projects.

Lateral Economics' 2025 analysis demonstrates that AAF generates substantial net benefits for the Australian community:

- In the central case, AAF delivers around \$58 million in gross annual benefits, compared with costs of only \$6.8 million, producing net benefits of \$51 million and a benefit–cost ratio of 8.5.
- In an optimistic scenario, benefits rise to \$84 million annually, with net benefits of \$78 million and a benefit–cost ratio of 12.3.
- Even in our pessimistic scenario, there are net benefits of \$30 million and a benefit-cost ratio of 5.4.

- Put simply, for every dollar spent on AAF, the community gains between \$5.40 and \$12.30 in benefits.¹⁸

Activities and Benefits

AAF runs “incubator projects” with partners such as NCI, Pawsey, Microscopy Australia, Astronomy Australia, Phenomics, and ACCESS-NRI. These pathfinder initiatives test solutions to complex trust and identity challenges – for example, implementing single sign-on, developing international assurance frameworks, and improving impact tracking. The lessons are then scaled for broader benefit across the ecosystem.

Beyond improving the ease of accessing shared networks, AAF also enhances the quality of that access improving cybersecurity and research integrity. It provides a consistent trust framework for managing sensitive data, reducing risks of foreign interference, privacy breaches, and system compromise. In effect, AAF allows researchers to focus on science rather than managing log-ins and compliance.

Counterfactual – Without AAF

Without AAF:

- Each institution would need to create its own identity management systems, leading to duplication of IT staff and infrastructure.
- Researchers would face a patchwork of logins and authorisation rules, undermining collaboration and productivity.
- Australia would risk isolation from international projects due to non-alignment with global standards.
- Sensitive data would be exposed to higher cybersecurity risks through fragmented, inconsistent frameworks.
- The absence of AAF would therefore result in higher costs, lower efficiency, weaker security, and reduced international engagement.

3.2.5. Atlas of Living Australia (ALA)

Core role

The ALA is Australia’s national biodiversity data infrastructure. It allows researchers, decision-makers and the community to contribute, access and analyse data on Australia’s plants, animals, and fungi. The ALA also designs, builds and manages cutting-edge biodiversity products and services for its partners. These products and services utilise global biodiversity

¹⁸ Lateral Economics (2025) Measuring the Economic Value of the Australian Access Federation, report prepared for the Australian Access Federation.

data standards and ALA expertise to enhance biodiversity data acquisition, management, and delivery across a suite of national biodiversity data programs.

Distinctive value and scale

ALA manages relationships with around 800–900 data custodians (a fixed-cost task others do not need to duplicate) and integrates disparate biodiversity data into a single information model (avoiding one-off, bespoke harmonisation). Indicatively, ALA is funded at \$5.5 million per annum from the Department of Education, roughly matched by CSIRO. The cumulative public investment in ALA is around \$80 million since its inception in 2010.

Policy, industry and science impacts

ALA is strongly embedded in environmental regulatory and policy workflows: around 75–85% of environmental impact assessments under the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation (EPBC) Act reportedly use ALA as a starting point. Furthermore, ALA data support Commonwealth State of the Environment reporting and feature in the recent Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) National Ecosystem Accounts. Ultimately, its key user group is Australia's science and research community, which gains significant benefit from the ALA, generating over 300 scientific publications annually, underpinned by ALA capability.

Public engagement and tools

A large public user base contributes species observations (e.g., via iNaturalist, NatureMapr, Birdlife, etc.) that are then expert-verified—expanding data coverage at low marginal cost and adding educational/recreational value. Software developers can also access the ALA's Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) via R/Python tools; ALA also builds and hosts core biodiversity data platforms for its national partners (e.g., Australian Virtual Herbarium, Australian Seed Bank Portal) and builds capabilities on a co-investment basis (e.g. MERIT for DCCEEW).

Biosecurity and knowledge gaps

ALA's core systems have recently been leveraged to establish a national biosecurity alerts service that notifies Commonwealth and state and territory authorities when priority species are detected—accelerating invasive-species detection and response. More broadly, ALA helps address significant knowledge gaps (e.g., around 70% of Australian species, and around 90% of insects, remain undescribed), improving national awareness of our natural environment.

How it responds to market failure

ALA is a classic public-good infrastructure: characterised by high fixed costs, large spillovers, and strong external benefits from standardisation. Its core functions—relationship management and data standardisation and harmonisation—create system-wide productivity gains; the

platform then multiplies value through policy use, industry compliance, citizen science, and research.

International positioning

As the Australian node of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the ALA ensures that Australian biodiversity information is available to support the international community, providing data with reciprocal benefits to Australian users. ALA's open-source software also supports the global Living Atlases program, allowing over 20 countries to establish sovereign biodiversity e-infrastructure capability. Combined with ALA's role leading the Oceania region for GBIF, there are significant science diplomacy benefits from the investment in the ALA.

3.2.6. Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN)

Core role

APPN is Australia's national phenomics research infrastructure, enabling high-throughput, deep and field phenotyping so plant traits can be measured, linked to genetics and climate, and translated into higher yields, quality and resilience.¹⁹ It is building a national, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)-aligned phenomics data layer to make these insights reusable at scale.

Scale and investment

Since 2023, APPN has expanded from three to nine nodes across most agricultural universities, offering seven controlled-environment sites, five field sites, and six mobile phenotyping units. Funding of \$132 million over five years roughly triples capacity and is co-funded by multiple parties.

What APPN provides

- **World-class phenotyping infrastructure:** including controlled-environment facilities, field sites, and mobile phenotyping units that enable crop studies under diverse and programmable growth conditions.
- **Advanced technologies and expertise:** robotics, imaging and sensing tools (RGB, hyperspectral, fluorescence, thermal, 3D), data analytics, and specialist knowledge in plant science, engineering, and software.
- **Specialised support and compliance:** qualified staff and systems to facilitate research with genetically modified plants and biosecurity-sensitive crops.
- **National data infrastructure:** a unified architecture that standardises how plant phenomics data are captured, managed, and shared across all APPN nodes.

¹⁹ The Australian Plan Phenomics Facility (APPF) was renamed the Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN) on 4 June 2024.

- **Open access and interoperability:** enables researchers, industry, and policymakers to access harmonised datasets, supporting reproducibility and cross-institutional collaboration.
- **Data integration and analytics:** links phenomics outputs (imaging, sensing, growth data) with genomics, agronomy, and environmental datasets, enabling advanced modelling and decision-support for crop improvement.

Illustrative use cases (innovation pathways)

X-ray computed tomography (CT) offers a major advance in assessing frost and heat damage in wheat by replacing labour-intensive manual inspections with rapid, high-resolution imaging. Whereas evaluating 100,000 wheat heads typically requires six staff over six months at a cost exceeding \$200,000, CT scanning reduces the task to around two months with a single operator. Effectively, it has reduced the labour costs to 1/18th of the previous method. In addition to substantial time and cost savings, the technology delivers non-destructive, three-dimensional imaging that provides far greater precision in detecting internal grain development and damage.

Late maturity α -amylase (LMA) screening in wheat has been improved through protocol revisions that both lower testing costs and enable earlier culling of susceptible lines.²⁰ According to a Grains Research and Development Corporation (GRDC) assessment, the revised approach delivers a strong benefit–cost ratio (BCR) of approximately 6.3:1, indicating substantial efficiency gains and value for breeders and growers.²¹

ArduCrop, a canopy-temperature sensing technology developed within the APPN at CSIRO's High Resolution Plant Phenomics Centre, has been licensed to Goanna Ag and integrated into commercial irrigation management tools such as GoField and WaterWise. These tools use real-time crop stress signals to optimise irrigation scheduling, reducing water use while sustaining yields. Independent assessments suggest potential savings in agricultural water use and delivery of significant economic value, estimated to be up to 806 gigalitres and \$769 million by 2030, respectively, across the agricultural sector.²²

Training and pipeline

The APPN supports capacity-building and knowledge transfer through technical seminars and internships, with 53 postgraduate awardees across 14 universities to date. Its outreach activities are also significant, hosting 518 facility tours and approximately 4,168 visitors

²⁰ LMA is a genetic defect that affects the quality of wheat. It is an enzyme that can develop in cereal grains just before harvest and partially break down starch, reducing grain quality and processing performance.

²¹ Marsden Jacob Associates (2024) Ex-post analysis of LMA Program, prepared for Grains Research Development Corporation, p. 11.

²² [Prospective Analysis of WaterWise](#) (2020), RTI International. Note that dollar values are expressed in 2020 dollar terms.

between 2017 and 2023, thereby strengthening engagement with researchers, students, and industry stakeholders.

Why it warrants public investment

The APPN tackles classic market failures in agricultural research— knowledge spillovers that mean individual researchers are not provided with sufficient incentive to stimulate R&D. It digitises research workflows and generates reusable data assets, disseminating knowledge and ensuring the spillovers occur. This delivers benefits through cost savings, accelerated breeding and deployment (bringing forward productivity gains), and option value from establishing an AI-ready national phenomics layer. While most new nodes are still ramping up, suggesting that attribution should remain conservative in the near term, measured returns to date are already strong.

3.2.7. Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)

Core role

ARDC develops and operates Australia’s national knowledge infrastructure for data. Its core services include the Nectar Research Cloud (elastic compute for research), the Thematic Research Data Commons (Planet, People/Health, and Humanities, arts, social sciences (HASS) and Indigenous domains), Research Data Australia (a discovery portal aggregating data from more than 100 organisations), Research Vocabularies Australia, persistent identifier services, and a suite of advisory and skills development programs.

What it provides in practice

Through its three Thematic Research Data Commons, the ARDC co-designs national, domain-ready platforms that integrate compute, storage, curated datasets, tools, and training. These platforms enable researchers, agencies, and industry to analyse and share data at scale. The Planet RDC focuses on building trusted data supply chains, delivering integrated FAIR datasets, supporting advanced modelling and analytics platforms, and embedding best practice in Indigenous data governance.

How value is created

ARDC targets the busy intersection of government, industry and research, where most operational spending and policy/action sit (e.g., environmental assessments). Its co-investment model crowds in partners—about \$3 for every ARDC \$1—a revealed-preference signal of uptake and value. Mature exemplars include Biosecurity Commons (now an operational service) and EcoCommons. ARDC’s EcoAcoustics work addresses a widespread pain-point—cheap sensors generating unaffordable backlogs—by providing rapid processing with management payoffs.

Data spaces and regional impact

ARDC is piloting trusted data spaces (European-style) that streamline legal agreements and automate data-sharing conditions—reducing administrative friction across departments. In the Pilbara SE project, a PwC evaluation identified productivity gains of up to \$1.4 billion over 10-years from de-duplicated data collection and shared analytics enabling quicker, more robust assessments.

How it responds to market failure

The ARDC addresses coordination and standardisation failures in research data by providing shared compute infrastructure, FAIR datasets, persistent identifiers, and governance frameworks. In doing so, it generates platform externalities and economies of scope that extend well beyond academia, supporting government and industry operations alike. This explains both the strong levels of co-investment and the ARDC's expanding portfolio of operational services.

3.2.8. Bioplatforms Australia (BPA)

Core role

The Bioplatforms Australia (BPA) is Australia's national genomics capability, spanning both laboratory and data-intensive activities. It builds and curates reference genomic libraries and conducts dynamic measurements such as population genetics across Australia's biodiversity. While its portfolio is broad, major program areas include biomedicine (around 50% of its activity) and agriculture (around 30%), with the remaining around 20% focused on biodiversity and environmental applications.

What BPA delivers

Foundational assets: build a genomic record of Australian biodiversity via Bioplatforms initiatives (plants, birds, reptiles/amphibians, threatened species) and the Australian Reference Genome Atlas (ARGA) with Genome Tracker.

Applied analytics: apply metagenomics and eDNA, supported by ARGA and BioCommons pipelines, to detect species presence/absence and monitor environmental change for impact assessments.

Functional resilience and option value: use Bioplatforms trait-focused genomics and diversity datasets to quantify genetic depth and resilience, guiding conservation, rehabilitation, and future ecosystem service planning.

Business model and partnerships

Referential libraries and infrastructure: BPA invests in the “boring but essential” referential omics libraries—backbone infrastructure such as genomics, proteomics, metabolomics,

synthetic biology, and bioinformatics—under NCRIS funding, delivered through a national network of state-of-the-art laboratories (18 facilities across Australia) and the Australian BioCommons digital platform. While BPA administers approximately \$0.25 billion over five years, funding around 20 centres of excellence (~350 FTE), much of its project-specific work is supported by external end-users such as government, industry, and other entities..

Operational model and data stewardship: operating similar to an active fund manager, BPA manages large-scale contracts (about 20,000 per year) serving over 3,000 researchers across universities, government, startups, and private sectors, facilitating access through fee-for-service models or collaborative partnerships. It curates significant data volumes—hundreds of terabytes of omics datasets—available via AWS-hosted portals, such as the Data Portal and ARGGA, enabling FAIR-aligned resource reuse.

Business model and strategic partnerships: BPA prefers joint public–private delivery, contracting private providers to capitalise capability and execute to the timeline. It fosters commercialisation via a dedicated pre-seed translation fund and incubation ecosystem, having already supported spin-offs such as Number 8 Bio, without any NCRIS equity involvement. Partners have included Munderoo/Fortescue, Rio Tinto, BHP, and the Australian Wine Research Institute (AWRI).

Innovation and dual use

BPA programs exemplify dual-purpose applications, such as venomous biota libraries that support both conservation and biodiscovery/therapeutics, and fungi initiatives that range from improving food safety to developing novel medicines.

How BPA responds to market failure

BPA addresses market failures in foundational, high-fixed-cost (refer to Box 3.1) genomics and standardisation. The reference libraries create non-rival assets that unlock spillovers in health, agriculture and environmental management. Their option value is significant: today's libraries underpin tomorrow's diagnostics, breeding, biosecurity, and ecosystem rehabilitation, with returns compounding as datasets expand and new use-cases emerge.

3.2.9. Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS)

Core role

IMOS is Australia's fully integrated national ocean observing system, operating at basin and regional scales across physical, chemical and biological domains. Established in 2006 and enabled by NCRIS, IMOS operates an extensive network of over 50 observing platforms, ranging from moorings and ocean gliders to acoustic telemetry arrays and coastal wave buoys, to capture long-term and systematic data across Australia's coastal and open ocean environments. All collected data are openly published via the Australian Ocean Data Network

(AODN) and complemented with near-real-time visualisations and contextual insights through OceanCurrent.

What it provides

IMOS brings together a coordinated suite of national observing platforms, including moorings, ship-of-opportunity sensors, ocean gliders, autonomous vehicles, and Argo profiling floats, to generate continuous, quality-controlled data streams. These open data resources underpin marine research, policy development, and operational decision-making. IMOS is delivered through a national consortium led by the University of Tasmania and involving key partners such as AIMS, the Bureau of Meteorology, CSIRO, SARDI, SIMS, and UWA.

Economic impact

An independent analysis by Lateral Economics estimated that Commonwealth investment in IMOS delivers a benefit–cost ratio between 7.6-12.0 to 1, with a net present value of approximately \$8.3 billion over 50 years, generating \$4.70 of benefit for every \$1 of investment into IMOS.²³

Use cases and users

IMOS data provide critical inputs to national weather and ocean forecasting systems, most notably the CSIRO–BoM–Defence Bluelink system that underpins maritime safety and naval operations. They support sustainable fisheries management, inform national State of the Environment reporting, and contribute to climate change assessments. Through the OceanCurrent platform and other data products, IMOS also delivers near real-time situational awareness of ocean conditions, including the development of cyclones and the onset of marine heatwaves.

Global integration and future directions

IMOS is a [Regional Alliance](#) of the Global Ocean Observing System, playing a key leadership role in this community.²⁴ As part of these efforts, IMOS sustains Australia’s long-term contribution to the international Argo program and is now expanding into Deep Argo, with sensors reaching depths of approximately 6 km to better quantify ocean heat content, salinity, and circulation—the fundamental drivers of sea-level rise and extreme events. In addition, IMOS produces the State and Trends of Australia’s Oceans report and is a critical data source for State of the Environment reporting, synthesising national ocean observations into accessible insights for policymakers and stakeholders.

²³ https://imos.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/IMOS_Annual_Highlights_electronic_-_2021.pdf

²⁴ Regional Alliance is the term used for regional contributors to the Global Ocean Observing System like IMOS. For further information, see: <https://goosocan.org/who-we-are/goos-regional-alliances/>.

How IMOS addresses market failure

IMOS addresses classic market failures in ocean observing, characterised by high fixed costs, indivisible network infrastructure, and extensive knowledge spillovers. By lowering access and integration costs through the AODN and providing sustained, decision-grade observations, IMOS delivers measurable productivity gains and risk-reduction benefits across government, industry, and research. These impacts align with the high benefit–cost ratios identified in independent evaluations.

3.2.10. Marine National Facility (MNF)

Core role

The Marine National Facility (MNF) underpins Australia’s blue-water research infrastructure through its flagship ocean-class vessel, the RV Investigator, providing multidisciplinary capabilities across oceanography, atmospheric science, geoscience, and marine biology. Commissioned in 2014 and becoming operational in 2015, the 94-meter vessel enables voyages from the tropical north to the Antarctic ice-edge. RV Investigator’s unique onboard platforms—such as its low-noise hull, retractable gondola and drop keels, state-of-the-art atmospheric laboratories, and a range of oceanographic and geophysical sensors—enable collection of critical ‘underway’ data ²⁵ (from seawater sampling to weather radar and ocean floor mapping) that cannot be matched by coastal monitoring or remote sensing alone.

Through these capabilities, MNF voyages generate invaluable ground-truth data for satellite calibration, long-term observation records, and global research models—supporting evidence-based policy, ecosystem stewardship, climate understanding, and capability development across Australia’s marine research community.

What it provides

MNF delivers a unique portfolio of national research assets. Its flagship vessel, the RV Investigator—the third in a line of MNF research ships—supports multidisciplinary blue-water research across atmospheric, oceanographic, geoscience, and biological domains, often integrating multiple disciplines within a single voyage. Tangible assets include more than 40 years of aggregated voyage datasets, which grow in scientific and economic value through continued reuse, as well as a pool of highly specialised research equipment valued in the tens of millions of dollars. Equally critical are the intangible assets: an experienced technical workforce with scarce expertise in shipboard systems configuration, instrumentation, and operations, ensuring world-class data quality and continuity.

²⁵ “Underway data collection” refers to continuous, real-time gathering of data from sensors distributed around the vessel (e.g. atmospheric, geophysical, seawater sampling) as the RV Investigator travels.

Access, utilisation and efficiency

Access to the MNF is merit-based, with voyage scheduling typically planned on a two-year horizon to account for feasibility, equipment requirements, navigation, permits, and clearances. Once approved, MNF provides “science-ready infrastructure”, including specialist technical staff, IT systems, hydrochemistry laboratories, and advanced seabed mapping capability, avoiding costly duplication across institutions that only occasionally operate at sea. Efficiency and productivity are further enhanced through supplementary projects, such as piggyback activities like instrument or float deployments, and transit science conducted between ports, ensuring maximum research return from every voyage.

Training and workforce

MNF invests in capability development through a dedicated annual training voyage for graduate and postgraduate students, as well as an Indigenous Scientists at Sea program that fosters participation and representation of Indigenous scientists in marine research. Most research voyages also host substantial student cohorts, providing hands-on experience in multidisciplinary ocean science. In parallel, the MNF’s ship-management contractor contributes to maritime workforce development by training cadets and supporting the progression of deck and bridge crews.

Linkages and national integration

The MNF operates as a cornerstone of Australia’s marine research ecosystem, maintaining strong ties with complementary national capabilities. It collaborates closely with IMOS to align long-term ocean observations, with the Southern Coastal Research Fleet to extend coverage into nearshore environments, with ARDC on data harmonisation, and with the Atlas of Living Australia for the integration and display of biological data. Partnerships with Geoscience Australia (e.g., seabed mapping) and the Bureau of Meteorology (real-time underway data feeds) further amplify whole-of-system benefits and ensure MNF outputs are embedded across research, operational, and policy domains.

Economic impact

CSIRO’s independent 2020 economic study, undertaken by RTI International, found that investment in the MNF yields a median benefit–cost ratio of 4.7:1, equivalent to generating \$4.70 in social and economic value for every \$1 invested. The study estimated a net present value of approximately \$2.4 billion, with returns driven by benefits such as improved seabed mapping, fisheries management, climate and weather forecasting, and heritage protection.²⁶

²⁶ [Impact Analysis of the Marine National Facility](#)

How MNF responds to market failure

The MNF embodies classic public-good characteristics, marked by high, indivisible capital costs and substantial knowledge spillovers, making collective funding the most efficient model. Its long-term datasets and specialist technical teams create significant option value for future research and policy needs, while its provision of “science-ready” services minimises duplication across institutions and lowers transaction costs across the research system.

3.2.11. National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)

Core role

The National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) is one of Australia’s two Tier-1 national high-performance computing (HPC) hubs, providing integrated HPC, cloud services, and curated national research datasets. It complements the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, with both centres coordinating closely to distribute computational services and enhance the resilience of computing services. Its flagship resources—the Gadi supercomputer, the Nirin cloud, and the National Research Data Repository—are all accessible through the web-based Australian Research Environment (ARE), which streamlines workflows and minimises data-movement frictions to enable large-scale, data-intensive research.

What it provides

The Gadi supercomputer—with more than 250,000 CPU cores, 930 TB of RAM, and 640 GPUs—supports workloads ranging from climate modelling to advanced materials research, with a 2023 upgrade boosting the performance of large-scale climate models by over 40%. NCI’s online storage capacity now exceeds 120 PB (approximately 80 PB active and 42 PB archival), while its curated national data collections reached about 24 PB in 2023–24, spanning domains such as climate and weather, geophysics, earth observation, astronomy, and genomics.

Users and partners

Nearly 7,000 researchers depend on NCI’s services, drawing from across Australia’s research and innovation system. Collaboration extends across the Australian National University (ANU), CSIRO, the Bureau of Meteorology, Geoscience Australia, leading universities, and state agencies. Strategic oversight is provided through an Advisory Board hosted by ANU, ensuring national alignment and governance.

NCI is a member of the Trillion Parameter Consortium, an international collaboration focused on creating large-scale generative AI models with trillion-parameter capabilities to address key challenges in science and engineering, while ensuring these models are trustworthy and reliable for research. NCI is also a member of the Accelerated Data Analytics and Computing

(ADAC) Institute which fosters international collaboration among HPC centres, with the purpose of advancing GPU-accelerated capabilities for academia, government, and industry.

Access and allocation

In collaboration with Pawsey, the centre supports the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS), which allocates over 750 million compute hours annually. NCRIS organisations receive around 40% of NCI's compute capacity through competitive national allocations, a process that is typically oversubscribed by a factor of three. Major collaborators also hold dedicated access rights; for example, the Bureau of Meteorology conducts climate research on NCI while running its operational weather forecasting on its own HPC systems.

NEESFF alignment (environmental and earth sciences)

Approximately 40.5% of the compute cycles used at NCI in the third quarter of 2025 (around 1 billion core hours) were for Earth and Environment (E&E) projects, according to Field of Research codes supplied by the researchers. For data storage, the fraction is even higher, with 60.0% of the long-term data storage (more than 36 petabytes) being used by this community. By hosting a significant number of E&E collections in the National Research Data Repository at NCI, E&E researchers can get started quickly without duplicating effort, benefit from data optimised for high-performance computing, and trust in the integrity of replicated datasets. NCI also works closely with E&E research groups to uplift their data products to domain standards, optimise them for HPC environments, consolidate them into more valuable collections, and publish them to national and international audiences.

Training and capability

NCI plays a leading role in building national capability, delivering training and upskilling programs in HPC, data science, and artificial intelligence (AI). It also provides user-focused services and support environments designed to broaden effective access, enabling researchers across disciplines to harness advanced computing and data resources fully.

How NCI addresses market failure

In 2023-24, NCI reported consolidated income of approximately \$37.4 million, diversified across collaboration income, NCRIS funding, grants, and other sources. As a shared, high fixed-cost platform that co-locates advanced compute with FAIR-aligned data collections, NCI addresses coordination and standardisation failures that individual institutions cannot efficiently resolve. In doing so, it generates system-wide productivity spillovers and accelerates the translation of research, consistent with Australia's national digital research infrastructure objectives.

3.2.12. National Sea Simulator (SeaSim)

Core role

The National Sea Simulator (SeaSim) at the Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS) is a globally distinguished marine experimental research facility, situated at AIMS headquarters near Cape Ferguson—approximately 50 km south of Townsville, Queensland. SeaSim provides researchers and collaborators with unique capabilities to conduct large-scale, long-duration studies under highly controlled environmental conditions.

SeaSim plays a central role in research on climate change impacts, coral bleaching, reef restoration, water quality, and marine biodiversity. It has supported pioneering projects such as assisted evolution of corals and large-scale coral aquaculture. It supports significant work in the areas of ecotoxicology and microplastics, water quality, marine diseases and pests, and biodiversity conservation, technology and innovation. In recognition of its vital national role, SeaSim received \$36.3 million in 2021 from NCRIS to support a significant expansion, thereby more than doubling its capacity and establishing a merit-based access program for researchers. The expansion, which includes new indoor and outdoor experimental zones, aims to broaden research potential and accelerate coral spawning and environmental simulation.²⁷ studies

What it provides and how it works

SeaSim operates under a technician-led model, whereby in-house specialists design, build, and manage complex experimental systems, in order to allow researchers to concentrate on scientific inquiry rather than technical setup. While this approach may appear to increase access costs under a cost-recovery framework, it significantly reduces overall research expenditure by substituting weeks of researcher effort with more efficient technician time. Furthermore, with the support of national funding, access to SeaSim is now allocated according to the merit of competing uses rather than the financial means of proponents which, if it can be done well, is arguably the most appropriate way to ration access to this scarce resource.

Coral experimentation and applications

A significant focus of SeaSim's research is coral experimentation under the Reef Restoration and Adaptation Program (RRAP). This work explores strategies to prevent coral bleaching, enhance thermal resilience, and develop large-scale aquaculture methods that could underpin future restoration efforts across the Great Barrier Reef and reefs globally.

SeaSim is the only national research aquarium in Australia and is regarded as globally unique in both capability and scale. Strategic plans include linking Australian research aquaria into a

²⁷ <https://www.bdmag.com.au/seasim-simulating-the-future/>

coordinated network to standardise methodologies, share expertise, and enhance national research productivity.

SeaSim tracks utilisation, outputs, and publications, with around 80% of experiments conducted collaboratively, many in partnership with James Cook University. A new project management and metadata system is being implemented to streamline reporting and automatically generate performance metrics for funding bodies.

How it responds to market failure

SeaSim addresses high fixed-cost capabilities that individual laboratories cannot efficiently replicate. Its benefits extend beyond immediate research outcomes to include significant public-good and non-use (existence) values associated with safeguarding the Great Barrier Reef and coral reefs globally, as well as option value for future restoration and adaptation efforts. This work is critical to underpinning emerging biodiversity credit schemes associated with nature-repair markets. Given the predominantly public-good nature of coral restoration and reef resilience at this time, government remains the primary and indeed only feasible client. At the same time, SeaSim has delivered practical operational gains, such as research into marine dredging that both reduced industry costs and enhanced environmental protection.

Furthermore, SeaSim is supporting research associated with the decommissioning of oil and gas infrastructure at end-of-life to guide better environmental practices and policy development.

3.2.13. Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre

Purpose and role

The Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre is one of Australia's two Tier-1 national HPC hubs, delivering high-performance computing, advanced data infrastructure, and expert support that catalyses breakthroughs across sectors—including astronomy, climate and environmental science, resources, health, and industry. It complements NCI, with both centres coordinating closely to distribute computational services and enhance resilience. Located in a purpose-built facility at Technology Park in Kensington, Perth, Pawsey hosts the Setonix supercomputer, an HPE Cray EX system—the most powerful research supercomputer in the Southern Hemisphere and one of the world's most energy-efficient systems

Pawsey provides an integrated research computing environment combining Setonix with scalable cloud, storage, and visualisation infrastructure, along with specialist technical expertise. In collaboration with NCI, the centre supports the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS), which allocates over 750 million compute hours annually. In addition, Pawsey runs a Partner Merit Allocation Scheme. Through the two schemes combined, Pawsey grants more than a billion compute hours annually to research projects across the country.

Users and communities

It serves universities, national science agencies and collaborative programs, and is tightly coupled to international efforts (e.g., running UK Met Office “next-generation” model development workloads). This strengthens Australia’s capability to localise and improve models for southern-hemisphere conditions.

Use-cases and outcomes (NEESFF-relevant)

Pawsey provides critical infrastructure for climate and weather modelling, regional downscaling, and environmental analytics, directly supporting public risk management in areas such as cyclone preparedness, water security, and agricultural planning. Its high-performance computing capability enables the kind of open-ended modelling and scenario testing that governments rely on for timely, evidence-based decision-making.

While formal field-of-research usage data are not publicly disclosed, it is clear that environmental and Earth sciences represent a substantial share of Pawsey’s workloads. The examples above, plus the centre’s Tier-1 role alongside NCI, indicate a material portion of annual compute serving NEESFF-aligned climate and environmental modelling.

How it responds to market failure

Pawsey addresses classic market failures in high-performance computing: indivisibility, as petascale systems are large, capital-intensive, and cannot be efficiently replicated by individual institutions; network spillovers, as shared expertise and data infrastructure lift productivity across the research system; and public-good knowledge outputs, including policy-relevant climate and hazard intelligence. By combining scale, reliability, and specialist staff, Pawsey transforms capital investment into national-level options for risk reduction and innovation, underpinning both scientific progress and informed decision-making.

3.2.14. Southern Coastal Research Vessel Fleet (SCRVF)

Core role

A coordinated coastal research vessel capability in southern Australia, the Southern Coastal Research Vessel Fleet (SCRVF) delivers vessels purpose-built for multidisciplinary research operations—oceanography, biological surveys, fisheries, environmental monitoring, and more—that individual commercial vessels are ill-suited to provide with efficiency or flexibility. The fleet includes vessels such as MRV Ngerin, RV Naturaliste, RV Linnaeus, and RV Djildjit, which are designed to run multiple work components concurrently, increasing productivity per voyage. Without this shared infrastructure, many essential research projects would either not proceed or would incur high cost and scheduling uncertainty via chartering.

The SCRVF is led by the South Australian Research and Development Institute (SARDI) in partnership with Western Australia's Department of Primary Industries and Regional Development (DPIRD), funded largely through NCRIS, and supported by the CSIRO Marine National Facility. It augments its core large vessels with smaller 18-20 metre patrol/research vessels to increase flexibility and coverage across southern waters. Plans are underway (business case and vessel replacement) to enhance operational capacity, increase geographic range, extend endurance, and integrate modern, modular science systems.

Access and cost efficiency

Typical operating costs are approximately \$10,000 per day, compared with up to \$20,000 per day for commercial charters, which often lack both the specialised configuration and availability required for marine research. The fleet provides research-ready platforms with predictable access, ensuring continuity for scientific programs. Current utilisation is around 40–50 days per year, with a substantial increase expected once the new vessel enters service. Western Australia's vessel is already operating at full capacity, while SARDI retains some flexible availability to accommodate additional research needs.

Integration and partnerships

SCRVF is closely integrated with IMOS. A substantial share of IMOS activities in South Australia are undertaken on the MRV Ngerin, and the planned fleet expansion will extend support to other IMOS nodes across southern Australia. In addition, the fleet has facilitated Argo float deployments through its connection with the National Infrastructure Sharing Facility (NISF), further strengthening Australia's ocean observing capability.

Why it's needed (market failure)

A national survey highlighted a substantial unmet demand for coastal research infrastructure, reflecting limited availability of state-run vessels and the high cost and lower suitability of commercial charters. SCRVF addresses these gaps by overcoming indivisibilities and coordination failures, providing fit-for-purpose vessels at competitive rates. In doing so, it reduces system-wide transaction costs, ensures more predictable access, and enables research activities that would otherwise be delayed, constrained, or prohibitively expensive. In a way, SCRVF, like some other NEESFF organisations, acts as a 'co-op'.

SCRVF delivers a research-configured coastal fleet that the private market cannot reliably supply at the right time, capability, or cost. By substituting scarce researcher effort with integrated vessel services, it generates positive spillovers across key domains—fisheries management, coastal climate and hazard assessment, and biosecurity surveillance. These are classic areas of public-good provision, offering a strong rationale for continued public co-funding and investment.

3.2.15. Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN)

Core role

TERN is Australia's national ecosystem observatory, providing world-class research infrastructure for long-term, standardised monitoring of terrestrial (and coastal) ecosystems. It operates a continental-scale network of field sites, plots and sensors—supplemented by remote sensing and landscape workflows—that generate model-ready data on vegetation, soils, carbon, water, and biodiversity. All data, samples, tools and protocols are openly accessible, enabling researchers, land managers and policymakers alike to detect, quantify and respond to ecosystem change with rigour.

What it provides

TERN delivers a national observatory and data services platform, operating year-round across all of Australia's major biomes—from arid deserts to alpine regions, coastal wetlands, and agricultural landscapes. Its open data are published under Creative Commons 4.0 licence (CC BY 4.0) through the TERN Data Discovery Portal, supported by tools for data submission (SHaRED), analysis and integration (EcoPlots, Ecolmages), and a cloud-based virtual research environment (CoESRA).

TERN also produces the Australia's Environment Report and associated Environmental Condition Scores, which integrate satellite observations with on-ground measurements to provide annual, policy-ready indicators at scales ranging from national to local (postcode) level.

Several TERN Supersites are formally recognised by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) as international land-product validation sites, supplying gold-standard ground truth for the calibration and validation of Earth-observation products worldwide.

A dedicated program within TERN is developing national-scale, regularly updated ecological data products with quantified uncertainty, converting TERN's field and remote-sensing datasets into machine-readable inputs for ecosystem models, benchmarking frameworks, and decision-support tools.

Applied outputs include the Threatened Species Index, which tracks changes in Australia's biodiversity, and the Ecological Monitoring System Australia (EMSA), which creates nationally consistent evidence for assessing project and program outcomes from government investment in Natural Resource Management and other landcare projects. These innovations demonstrate how TERN's monitoring capability is translated into on-ground management outcomes, directly supporting conservation and land administration.

International positioning

TERN is a founding member of the Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (GERI) and an active participant in the International Long Term Ecological Research (ILTER) network and

FluxNet (a global network of ecosystem–atmospheric flux measurement sites). Through these partnerships, TERN contributes to the development of interoperable, standardised, and harmonised datasets, strengthening the global evidence base needed to address pressing environmental challenges, as well as providing data to help Australia meet its obligations under various treaties including the:

1. **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).** Australia submits National Reports to the CBD every four years and TERN’s ecosystem monitoring data contributes to these reports through the relevant government agencies responsible for meeting national reporting requirements.
2. **United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).** Australia submits annual National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Nationally Determined Contributions, and Biennial Transparency Reports to the UNFCCC. Australian government agencies responsible for meeting these national reporting requirements call on TERN data for vegetation structure, biomass and GHG flux measurements in accordance with guidelines set down by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
3. **Paris Agreement.** Australian Government agencies draw on TERN flux data and benefits of TERN cal/val services to help meet Australia's commitments under the Paris Agreement.

Training and engagement

TERN invests in education, training, and outreach to strengthen national capacity for ecosystem data use. Its activities include training manuals in data use and field techniques, regular webinars, a biennial science symposium, and targeted knowledge-brokering initiatives that connect researchers with government agencies, industry partners, and land managers.

How TERN responds to market failure

TERN addresses market failures in long-term, standardised ecosystem observation, providing environmental information that would not otherwise exist without national-scale research infrastructure. The benefits compound over time through interoperability, reduced transaction costs, and broad data reuse across agencies and sectors. At the same time, TERN recognises that detecting genuine ecological change requires sustained observation for decades at the cost of millions of dollars per year, underscoring the importance of its long-horizon commitment.

4. Pilot impact assessment: quantitative estimates

4.1. Introduction

In this section we present quantitative estimates of the benefits and costs of NEESFF. This is based on:

- existing CBA studies for AAF, AuScope, IMOS (all by Lateral Economics) and MNF (by RTI International for CSIRO) and ALA (by Alluvium in 2016); and
- new analysis in three case studies of the NEESFF organisations for which the best data and information was available for quantification of benefits at this stage, namely:
 - ALA;
 - APPN; and
 - TERN.

The benefit estimates we present as part of the case studies should be considered as indicative. They are based on available information and no new primary data (e.g. via a survey) have been collected. We realise that we may have only scratched the surface regarding the range of benefits offered by the NEESFF organisations, as many of the organisations are engaged in a wide range of activities and research partnerships, delivering diverse and potentially huge benefits. In the future, the benefit estimates could be improved by a larger and more in-depth study of each organisation, supplemented by survey data—e.g. of the WTP for the research outputs of each organisation, enabling us to quantify non-use existence values.

Due to data limitations (i.e. not having sufficient time series financial data for the NEESFF organisations), we estimate benefits and costs for a single year based on available data. For the purposes of providing indicative estimates of RoI this should be sufficient, but in some cases it may overstate net benefits where large capital investments have been made in the past and largely depreciated (i.e. written off in an accounting sense) and the cost assumption does not properly reflect true annual costs (e.g. if we included an annual charge for the eventual replacement of capital via a renewals annuity). On the other hand, depreciation could also be *less* than standard depreciation schedules allow to be expensed, which would leave net benefits *understated*.

Overall, regardless of the true extent of depreciation, we expect it is most likely we are understating benefits because it is challenging to model the full array of NEESFF organisation activities

4.2. Results from existing CBA studies

The findings of existing CBA studies are summarised in Table 4.1. There are a range of benefit-cost ratios generally well in excess of 1, suggesting benefits are significant multiples of costs and high RoIs for funds invested in these organisations.

Table 4.1. Results of existing CBAs for NEESFF organisations

Organisation	Benefit-cost ratio (Central case)	Source
AAF	8.5	Lateral Economics (2025)
ALA	3.5	Alluvium (2016)
AuScope	15.0	Lateral Economics (2016)
IMOS	4.7	Lateral Economics (2021)
MNF	4.7	RTI International (2020)
Average benefit-cost ratio	7.3	

Note: The studies differ in terms of their methodologies and discount rates, but nonetheless are indicative of the magnitudes of expected benefit-cost ratios.

4.3. Case study 1: Atlas of Living Australia (ALA)

4.3.1. Overview of benefits

Based on our interview with ALA staff and desktop research, we have identified various benefit items, including the following.

1. **Transaction Cost Savings for Biodiversity Data Users.** ALA manages relationships with 800–900 data providers, including museums, government agencies, and citizen science groups. By centralising this function, ALA spares researchers, consultants, and government bodies from having to negotiate data access and harmonisation individually. This represents a substantial saving in transaction costs across the biodiversity sector.
2. **Standardisation and Data Integration Savings.** ALA brings together a vast range of biodiversity data in diverse formats and converts it into a unified information model. This avoids duplication of effort across organisations that would otherwise need to spend significant time and resources cleaning and standardising data. The availability of integrated datasets allows users to focus on analysis and decision-making rather than technical data wrangling.
3. **Environmental Consulting Industry Use.** Environmental consultants rely on ALA data when preparing impact assessments and regulatory approval documents. The platform streamlines access to authoritative species distribution information, reducing

the staff hours and costs required to undertake such work. By lowering compliance costs for development approvals, ALA contributes to faster project delivery and efficiency in the consulting sector.

4. **Government and Policy Use.** Government agencies use ALA data extensively in conservation planning, threatened species management, and habitat restoration programs. Ready access to reliable biodiversity records reduces the need for costly duplicate surveys and monitoring activities. This ensures that scarce public funds for environmental management are applied more effectively.
5. **Citizen Science Contributions.** ALA enables and amplifies the contributions of citizen scientists, who provide millions of species observations through platforms such as mobile applications. These contributions represent a substantial resource that would otherwise require professional ecologists to collect at significant cost. By harnessing the voluntary efforts of the public, ALA expands the evidence base for biodiversity science at low cost to government.
6. **Educational and Recreational Value.** The ALA website is widely used by schools, students, and the general public as a way of exploring Australia's biodiversity. It provides an accessible entry point to science education and fosters public engagement with environmental issues. The value of this use can be seen in the time people choose to spend exploring the site. Economic analysis typically imputes a value to people's time and we do so here.
7. **Biosecurity and Early Detection of Invasive or Undescribed Species.** ALA assists in the detection of undescribed species and plays a role in monitoring biosecurity threats. Earlier detection of invasive species incursions can prevent substantial economic and environmental damage. By acting as an early warning system, ALA delivers potentially very large avoided costs in pest and disease management.
8. **Research Output and Knowledge Creation.** ALA underpins a growing body of scientific research in biodiversity and ecology by providing the data infrastructure needed for publication-quality analysis. The platform reduces barriers to knowledge creation and amplifies the return on investment in environmental science. Research supported by ALA contributes to policy, conservation, and broader scientific understanding.

In the next sub-section we quantify those benefit items for which we have reasonable information to make an estimate.

4.3.2. Quantification of benefits

Data access costs avoided—researchers

First we estimate the annual avoided cost for researchers who obtain data via ALA. Our assumptions and calculation is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2. Calculation: Data access costs avoided—researchers

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Registered users	141,759	ALA Year in Review 2023-24, p. 6.
B	Proportion of registered users who may need to negotiate access per year	10%	We assume ALA's current registered user base has been built up over the last ten years, and hence a reasonable estimate of the number of users each year who register for ALA is one-tenth (10%). We assume this proportion each year would need to access data sets they access via ALA some other way.
C	Time to obtain access to data sets (hrs)	1	Assumption we consider conservative given accessing data sets can be time consuming, particularly if there is an application process requiring a justification for why the researcher needs access to the data.
D	Value of time (\$/hr) - in paid employment incl. on costs	91.64	Based on the Office of Impact Assessment (2024) default values, updated to account for wage inflation between 2023 and 2025.
E	Total annual benefit (\$M)	1.3	E = A x B x C x D

Data access costs avoided-institutions

We assume that each of the approximately 850 data providers to ALA avoid the cost of one day of ICT staff time because they can make their data available via ALA rather than some other means. Using an estimate of average ICT salaries, we estimate this annual benefit at \$0.9 million (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3. Calculation: Data access costs avoided–institutions

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Data providers	850	Based on ALA's estimate of 800 to 900 providers.
B	Avoided days per year of time	1	Assumption we consider conservative based on potential workload of institutions having to manage their own data sharing service.
C	Cost per FTE	\$267,401	Based on CAUDIT data and assuming 75% on-costs, as per Office of Impact Assessment Guidelines
D	Working days per year	250	Based on 52 weeks per year x 5 days/week and subtracting 10 public holidays
E	Total annual benefit (\$ million)	0.9	E = A x B x (C / D)

Industry use benefits

Our assumptions and calculation of the annual benefit to industry of using ALA data are presented in Table 4.3. Given the value of ALA data in commercial applications, such as environmental impact assessment reports, this ends up being a significant quantifiable benefit.

Table 4.3. Calculation: Industry use benefits

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Regular users	1,100	ALA (2023) Partnering for impact with Australian industry
B	Value of data per user	\$5,000	By analogy with the average cost of an industry data service like IBISWorld. We assume that the regular industry users of ALA data are using it in consulting projects, and without ALA providing data, they would incur significant costs obtaining equivalent data.
C	Total benefit annually (\$M)	5.5	A = B x C

Other researcher benefits

We calculate other benefits to researchers, particularly the contribution of ALA data to journal publications, in Table 4.5. Note that there is an implicit assumption that the benefit conveyed by a journal publication is at least the value of time spent by researchers to produce it.

Table 4.5. Calculation: Other researcher benefits

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Journal articles published	200	ALA Year in Review 2023-24, p. 6.
B	Contribution to journal article	10%	Assumed contribution of ALA data to journal article.
C	Average researcher hours to produce journal article	100	This is based on online survey data on the median time to write a refereed journal article; see Kenny, J. & Fluck, A.E. (2018) "Research workloads in Australian universities", Australian Universities' Review, vol. 60, no. 2, p. 31; https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1188994.pdf
D	Value of time (\$/hr) - in paid employment incl. on costs	91.64	Based on the Office of Impact Assessment (2024) default values, updated to account for wage inflation between 2023 and 2025.
E	Total annual benefit (\$M)	0.2	E = A x B x C x D

Biodiversity benefits

We estimate the potential annual benefit of ALA to protecting Australia's biodiversity in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6. Calculation: Biodiversity benefits

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Required annual spending per year to improve ecosystems (\$ million)	2,100	PwC (2022) A nature-positive Australia - The value of an Australian biodiversity market, p. 5.
B	Percentage improvement	0.1%	Conservative assumption that the availability of data via ALA increases the efficiency of biodiversity protection efforts by 1/1000 (i.e. 0.1%)
C	Total annual benefit (\$M)	2.1	C = A x B

Consumer surplus benefits

One of the significant benefit items from ALA is the benefit people get from viewing the data and learning about flora and fauna of interest to them (Table 4.7). Implicit in our calculation of this benefit based on the value of time is that the gross benefit to someone of visiting the ALA site is at least double the value of time they spend on the site.

Table 4.7. Calculation: Consumer surplus

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Sessions per year (million)	6.74	ALA website traffic data for 2024.
B	Time per session (hrs)	0.1	Assumption
C	Proportion of users from Australia	90%	We assume the bulk of visitors to ALA are Australian
D	Proportion accessing in work time	10%	We assume a small proportion of visitors are accessing it in work time
E	Value of time (\$/hr) - not in paid employment	39.81	Based on the Office of Impact Assessment (2024) default values, updated to account for wage inflation between 2023 and 2025.
F	Value of time (\$/hr) - in paid employment incl. on costs	91.64	As above.
G	Benefit as a multiple of value of time spent on the site	2	Assumption reflective of the significant value of the high quality information provided by ALA
H	Gross annual benefit (\$ million)	54.6	$H = A \times B \times C \times (D \times F + (1 - D) \times E) \times G$
I	Time cost of accessing ALA site (\$ million)	27.3	$I = A \times B \times C \times (D \times F + (1 - D) \times E)$
J	Total annual benefit (\$M)	27.3	J = H - I

Long-tail benefits

In our case studies, we include a 'long-tail' benefit item similar to what LE included in its 2019 valuation of the Census for the ABS. This is to capture various benefits that we know are attributable to NEESFF organisations, based on our desktop research and interviews, but which are challenging to quantify individually. We use the logic of the '80-20' rule, otherwise known as the Pareto principle, to justify the inclusion of long-tail benefits equal to 25% of quantifiable benefits—i.e. the 20 on top of the 80 in the 80-20 rule. Based on our previous calculations of benefits this works out at \$5.2 million annually—i.e. 25% x \$20.8 million.

4.3.3. Costs

In the modelling, the annual cost of ALA is assumed to be \$10.2 million, based on figures provided by ALA. Additionally, we assume a 20% marginal cost of public funds, which adds \$2.0 million onto the annual cost of ALA.²⁸

Box 4.3.3: The marginal cost of public funds

When governments raise revenue through taxation, they typically impose 'hidden' costs. The dollars collected are not themselves a loss to the economy as they are taken from some and given to others. However taxes change behaviour: they can discourage work, saving, or investment, and they impose administrative and compliance costs. And each of these things typically reduces the productive capacity of the economy. Economists capture this idea with the concept of the marginal cost of public funds (MCPF). The MCPF measures the additional economic cost to society of raising an extra dollar of tax revenue.

In the modelling here, the assumed 20% marginal cost of public funds means that ALA's \$10.2 million cost is adjusted upward to \$12.24 million. This reflects the idea that the true resource cost of funding a public program is higher than its budgetary outlay, because the tax necessary to pay for it carries its own economic burden.

²⁸ This is based on Australian Treasury estimates of the marginal excess burden of income tax and GST of 21 and 19 cents per dollar of revenue, respectively. See <https://treasury.gov.au/sites/default/files/2019-03/TWP2015-01.pdf>, p. 53.

4.3.4. CBA results

Our indicative CBA results for ALA are presented in Table 4.8. These estimates are based on available information and may significantly understate the overall benefits. Nonetheless they show ALA delivering a strong RoI, with a BCR of 2.1. This means that for every dollar of costs, \$3.80 in benefits to the community are generated. This BCR is similar to the RoI for ALA estimated by Alluvium in 2016 of 3.5.

Table 4.8. CBA results, annual–Atlas of Living Australia (ALA)

	\$ million
Benefits	
Data access costs avoided - researchers	1.3
Data access costs avoided - institutions	0.9
Industry users	5.5
Other researcher benefits	0.2
Biodiversity benefits	2.1
Consumer surplus	27.3
Long-tail benefits	9.3
<i>Total benefits</i>	46.6
Costs	
Operating costs	10.2
Marginal cost of public funds	2.0
<i>Total costs</i>	12.2
Net benefits	34.4
Benefit-cost ratio	3.8

4.4. Case study 2: Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN)

4.4.1. Overview of benefits

Based on our interview with APPN staff and desktop research, we have identified several benefit items that could be quantified, including the following.

1. **Agricultural productivity.** This encompasses a wide range of benefits:
 - a. APPN accelerates breeding by automating and digitising plant measurements. APPN-supported phenotyping helps optimise production in high-value

- horticulture (tomatoes, berries, mushrooms). Additionally, APPN supports controlled environment testing of crops like medicinal cannabis.
- b. Benefits could include improvements in water efficiency, fertiliser use, or yield stability across hectares of cropping.
 - c. APPN's work can reduce costs in developing new crop protection products. APPN facilities allow lower-cost field trials and more efficient screening of products.
 - d. Plant pathogen detection and crop protection—APPN deploys Optical/AI systems for early disease detection and can cut fungicide use.²⁹
2. **Labour and time savings in research.** Automated robotic glasshouses can grow and monitor thousands of plants simultaneously. One phenotyping robot replaces dozens of manual researchers.
 3. **Education and training.** APPN nodes train PhD students, postdoctoral fellows, and technicians.
 4. **Data services.** APPN generates large plant trait datasets with long-term non-use values, including quasi-option values relating to later commercial development or use for medicinal purposes. This data is shared via AAF.³⁰

29

<https://groundcover.grdc.com.au/innovation/precision-agriculture-and-machinery/phenomics-to-improve-disease-management-and-resistance-breeding>

30

<https://trust.aaf.edu.au/project/enabling-national-and-international-researchers-with-open-access-to-their-state-of-the-art-phenotyping/>

4.4.2. Quantification of benefits

Agricultural benefits–water savings

We estimate significant benefits from the Arducrop technology which APPN contributed to the development of in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9. Calculation: Agricultural benefits–water savings

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Lower bound (ML)	179,000	APPN Summary of Outputs and Impact 2009-2025, p. 12.
B	Upper bound (ML)	2,476,000	As above.
C	Price of annual temporary water (\$/ML)	200	Based on desktop review of water pricing in Murray Darling Basin; e.g. https://elders.com.au/for-farmers/market-insights/latest-water-update/
D	APPN contribution (lower bound)	25%	Advice from APPN regarding their relative contribution to the Arducrop project.
E	APPN contribution (upper bound)	50%	As above.
F	Annual benefit (average), \$ million	99.6	$((A + B)/2) \times C \times ((D + E)/2)$

LMA screening

We use the average estimated annual benefit of LMA screening over 2025-26 to 2034-35 of \$1.1 million annually in our CBA.³¹ The bulk of this benefit (around 88%) is related to avoided costs from ruling out the further development of particular breeding lines due to the LMA screening.³² The remainder of the benefit comes from an increase in wheat yields.

Research benefits

We estimate a benefit to the research community from research supported by APPN in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10. Calculation: Research benefits

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Citations	11,671	APPN Summary of Outputs and Impact 2009-2025, p. 5.
B	Years over which citations accumulated	16	Based on the 16-year coverage of the APPN summary report.
C	Value to researchers of each citation (hrs)	8	Assumption that each APPN research paper provides a value equivalent to one day's work on the journal article it is cited in.
D	Value of time (\$/hr) - in paid employment incl. on costs	91.64	Based on the Office of Impact Assessment (2024) default values, updated to account for wage inflation between 2023 and 2025.
E	Total annual benefit (\$M)	0.5	E = (A / B) x C x D

³¹ Marsden Jacob Associates (2024, p. 35).

³² Ibid., p. 21.

Human capital

We estimate a benefit from APPN's training of postgraduate students in Table 4.11. Note we use an annuity factor to convert an annual value, the annual wage premium, into a present value (PV), assuming a certain discount rate and time period (Box 4.1).

Table 4.11. Calculation: Human capital

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Students trained	53	APPN Summary of Outputs and Impact 2009-2025, p. 7.
B	Years of operation	16	Based on the 16-year coverage of the APPN summary report.
C	Unit benefit - annual wage premium	30,000	Assumption based on desktop research of salary differences between senior research scientists and lab technicians.
D	Annuity factor (4.25%, 30 years)	16.78	Annuity factor calculated based on a 4.25% discount rate over 30 years); i.e. the lifetime value of the wage premium associated with the training. See Box 4.1 below)
E	Total annual benefit (\$M)	1.7	E = (A / B) x C x D

Box 4.1. What is an annuity factor?

An annuity factor is the present value (PV) of a stream of equal payments received over a fixed number of periods, discounted at a given interest rate. It answers the question: What is the value today of receiving one unit of currency each period for n periods at discount rate r ?

The formula is:

$$AF = ((1 - r)^n) / r$$

Annuity factors are commonly used in cost-benefit analysis and finance to convert a recurring flow of costs or benefits into an equivalent present value.

Long-tail benefits

As in the other case studies we estimate long-tail benefits as 25% of quantified benefits, which amounts to around \$27.1 million annually for APPN.

4.4.3. Costs

In the modelling, the annual cost of APPN is assumed to be \$16.1 million, based on figures provided by APPN. As in the other studies, we assume a 20% marginal cost of public funds, which adds \$2.9 million onto the annual cost of APPN.

4.4.4. CBA results

Our indicative CBA results for APPN are presented in Table 4.12. These estimates are based on available information and may significantly understate the overall benefits. Nonetheless they show APPN delivering a very strong RoI, with a benefit-cost ratio of 6.7. This means that for every dollar of costs, \$6.70 in benefits to the community are generated.

Table 4.12. CBA results, annual–Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN)

	\$ million
Benefits	
Agriculture (water savings)	99.6
LMA screening benefit	1.1
Research benefits	0.5
Human capital	1.7
Long-tail	25.7
<i>Total benefits</i>	<i>128.6</i>
Costs	
Operating costs	16.1
Marginal cost of public funds	3.2
<i>Total costs</i>	<i>19.3</i>
Net benefits	109.3
Benefit-cost ratio	6.7

4.5. Case study 3: TERN

4.5.1. Overview of benefits

Based on our interview with TERN staff and desktop research, we have identified several benefit items that could be quantified, including the following.

1. **Improved biodiversity conservation and land management.** TERN's Threatened Species Index is a centralised, standardised database of over 25,000 time-series datasets, which reduces duplication in data collection and leverages existing monitoring programs, saving government money compared to setting up new structures. It is now used by the ABS as Australia's headline biodiversity indicator within the sustainability theme of the "Measuring What Matters" framework. This means that management actions informed by TERN data have a direct role in tracking and improving biodiversity outcomes at a national scale. Even modest improvements in recovery rates can generate large economic benefits by avoiding the costs associated with species decline, such as reduced tourism appeal, degraded ecosystem services resulting in reduced productivity, and higher land management expenses. There is no doubt Australians have a WTP to protect or improve biodiversity, and hence there is likely a significant WTP for TERN's activities (Box 4.5.1).

Box 4.5.1 The value Australians place on biodiversity

There are several estimates of the value Australians place on biodiversity, often derived from economic valuation studies using methods such as willingness-to-pay surveys and cost-benefit analyses.

Willingness-to-Pay Estimates

A 2003 study in Victoria found that people were willing to pay between \$160 million (A\$118 per household) and \$340 million (A\$252 per household) annually to conserve 700 endangered species, and \$40–84 million (\$29–\$61 per household) per year for Leadbeater's possum conservation.³³

Another study using a discrete choice experiment found Australians willing to pay A\$1.87 per household per year for 20 years to achieve a one percentage point improvement in the status of the great desert skink, while less-valued communities were as low as A\$0.12 per household per year.³⁴

Biodiversity Market and Economic Benefit Estimates

A PwC analysis suggests that a well-developed Australian biodiversity market could unlock up to \$137 billion by 2050.³⁵ Direct annual spending on conservation of threatened species in Australia was estimated at a lower bound of \$130 million in 2022.³⁶ Incidentally, to restore Australia's degraded ecosystems, PwC estimates annual expenditure of \$2 billion per year for the next 20 years would be required.³⁷

Valuation Methods and Policy Relevance

These figures are based on contingent valuation, discrete choice experiments, and ecosystem service benefit models, all aiming to capture non-market values that Australians place on species and ecological communities.

2. **Climate and carbon accounting benefits.** TERN provides long-term data on carbon, water, and energy fluxes across ecosystems, which are critical for understanding how landscapes respond to the impacts of both land use and climate change. This data

³³ Cited in <https://www.cbd.int/financial/values/australia-valuation.pdf>, p. 11.

³⁴

https://www.nespthreatenedspecies.edu.au/media/g0miszms/6-1-economic-valuation-of-multiple-threatened-species-findings-factsheet_v2.pdf

³⁵

<https://www.pwc.com.au/environment-social-governance/nature-positive-australia-value-of-australian-biodiversity-market.html?icid=biodiversity-ofn-internal-organic-article>

³⁶ Ibid., p. 17.

³⁷ Ibid., p. 5.

underpins more accurate carbon sequestration estimates and strengthens the integrity of carbon markets. By reducing uncertainty in offsets and credits, TERN helps avoid the higher transaction costs that come with unverifiable or contested carbon accounting.

3. **Satellite calibration and validation (Cal/Val) savings.** From 2030, earth observation (EO) data could, according to the World Economic Forum and Deloitte, add \$703 billion GDP to the global economy while informing management actions that eliminate 2 gigatonnes of greenhouse gas emissions per year.³⁸ In Australia, EO data is directly adding more than AUD \$280 million to the Australian economy and with secondary impacts, the total contribution reached over AUD \$2.5 billion in 2020, according to CSIRO estimates.³⁹ Nevertheless, Australia has no viable domestic satellites to collect environmental data. Instead, it uses data collected by international satellite sensors and missions, in a large part due to the quality of cal/val services Australia provides to the world.

In particular, TERN's SuperSites have gained remarkable international recognition in the EO sector. For example, Copernicus, the European Union's Earth Observation and Monitoring program, operates a Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV) program for which TERN has been a collaborator since 2017. During that time, GBOV has leveraged TERN SuperSite data, uploading nearly 5 TB of TERN data, comprised of more than 22 million individual reference measurements. These have been converted into nearly 537,000 data products, which have been downloaded 1,437 times by users worldwide. Globally, the International Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) Working Group on Calibration and Validation (WGCV) identifies 56 locations worldwide as key reference sites for EO validation. Thirteen TERN SuperSites are included in this select group (23% of total sites globally).

As an example, a data sharing partnership between NASA and TERN has contributed to delivering precise information on water and carbon exchanges via several critical missions.

- The SMAP Satellite ensures better weather forecasting (e.g., earlier warning of droughts) and improved predictions of agricultural productivity, with more accurate measurements of global water and carbon movements.
- The ECOSTRESS mission provides critical climate data to scientists, helping them to better understand how crops, the biosphere and the global carbon cycle respond to water availability and drought.

³⁸ <https://www.weforum.org/publications/amplifying-the-global-value-of-earth-observation/>

³⁹ <https://www.csiro.au/en/research/technology-space/astronomy-space/Earth-observation>

- NASA's GEDI mission uses space-borne LiDAR to measure the structure of forests in high-resolution and 3D, while TERN's ground and airborne-based LiDAR data are used to validate the space-borne LiDAR data.

TERN facilities deliver substantial benefits to Australia by ensuring the accuracy, reliability, and long-term accessibility of satellite EO data from these international missions (Box 4.5.2). According to TERN, it is quite common for satellite products developed using only northern hemisphere sites to misrepresent Australian conditions. Hence, the contribution of TERN reference sites ensures the availability of high value EO data domestically that are relevant to the Australian continent and therefore essential to the operation of Australian industry, research and government.

Box 4.5.2. Cal/Val for satellites

Calibration and validation (cal/val) activities are essential to ensure that satellite-based measurements are accurate, reliable, and comparable across time and missions. Cal/val ensures satellite measurements remain accurate and reliable by correcting sensor biases and validating outputs against trusted ground and airborne observations. It is a continuous process that underpins confidence in satellite data for weather, climate, disaster response, and policy applications.

The calibration process adjusts and maintains satellite sensors against known references, both pre-launch (laboratory standards) and in orbit (onboard sources, solar/lunar observations). This corrects for sensor drift and instrument biases.

The validation process independently assesses satellite data accuracy by comparing outputs with trusted ground-based, airborne, or other satellite observations. Field campaigns and stable natural targets (e.g. deserts, oceans, Antarctica) are widely used.

Robust cal/val underpins confidence in satellite-derived products, which are relied upon for weather forecasting, climate monitoring, natural disaster management, and policy decision-making. Cal/val is not a one-off exercise but a continuous process throughout the satellite mission lifecycle to ensure data integrity and long-term consistency.

4. **Agricultural productivity improvements.** Through its partnership with the Australian Long-Term Agroecosystem Research network (ALTAR), TERN monitors greenhouse gas intensity, water use, and productivity under a range of land-use practices. This evidence helps farmers and policymakers identify land management strategies that

reduce the costs of inputs, such as fertilisers and water, while maintaining or even improving yields. In this way, TERN contributes to both agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability. In the agricultural sector, farmers need to know whether their soils are actively storing carbon and TERN's network of eddy co-variance flux towers can help farmers determine this. Instruments on the towers measure the real-time exchange of gases (especially CO₂), water and energy between plants, soil and air and some of TERN's towers permanently monitor this exchange on farmland. TERN provides the data essential both for refining soil carbon models and for developing management practices that improve soil and produce a productive, resilient environment. Ultimately, TERN data help farmers navigate and evaluate complex management decisions, including those potentially leading to recarbonisation of soils and carbon-neutral agriculture.⁴⁰

5. **Avoided costs of poor land management.** TERN's standardised long-term monitoring helps detect and anticipate ecological stressors such as fire, drought, and biodiversity loss. By providing early warnings and robust evidence for planning, TERN reduces the likelihood of costly mismanagement. Even a small improvement in preparedness for a major bushfire or drought⁴¹, attributable to TERN's data, can translate into significant avoided economic and social damages (Box 4.5.3).

6. **Avoided costs in agricultural irrigation water regulation.** The Australian Bureau of Statistics' (ABS) has replaced its survey-based irrigation estimates methodology for irrigated agricultural water use in both its Water and National Ecosystem Accounts with TERN's Evapotranspiration (ET) model, providing significant economic benefits to the community, including budgetary savings for government⁴². For example, the satellite and ground-based data integrated into TERN's model offer spatially explicit, scientifically validated estimates, reducing costly errors in water accounting that can lead to misallocation of resources. The ET model will also eliminate recurring survey administration costs.

7. **Avoided costs in conservation management.** The Australian Government makes significant investments (around \$420 million annually) through initiatives such as Natural Resource Management (NRM) to improve the stewardship of Australia's environment and the sustainable management of natural resources. TERN's Ecological

⁴⁰ <https://www.tern.org.au/news/flux-research-carbon-sequestration/>

⁴¹ <https://www.tern.org.au/news/satellite-eyes-in-the-sky/>

⁴² <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/environment/environmental-accounts/water-account-australia/latest-release>

Monitoring System Australia (EMSA)⁴³ has provided the standard methods to enable natural resource managers and ecologists to collect, manage and deliver quality, repeatable data for decision-making, and strengthen the evidence used to assess project outcomes. Results help to better prioritise future investments by government in NRM projects.

8. **Research efficiency and avoided duplication.** TERN has supported the production of around 3,000 peer-reviewed publications, reflecting its deep integration into the research community. Because its open data saves research teams from having to conduct expensive and time-consuming fieldwork, TERN enhances research efficiency and reduces duplication. This translates into large savings in labour and project costs across Australia's environmental science sector.

9. **Education, training, and international collaboration benefits.** TERN's data portal is internationally accredited and globally recognised, providing a trusted platform for research and researcher training. It supports the development of students and early-career researchers by giving them access to high-quality datasets and tools on an open-access basis, while also strengthening Australia's role in international research collaborations. This capacity building yields long-term economic and scientific benefits by fostering a technically skilled workforce and attracting international partnerships and funding and is seen as a model to other countries.

⁴³ <https://emsa.tern.org.au/about-us>

4.5.2. Quantification of benefits

Biodiversity conservation

In Table 4.13 we present our assumptions for and calculation of the biodiversity conservation benefit of TERN.

Table 4.13. Calculation: Biodiversity conservation–TERN

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Required annual spending per year to improve ecosystems (\$ million)	2,100	PwC (2022) A nature-positive Australia - The value of an Australian biodiversity market, p. 5.
B	Percentage improvement	0.1%	Conservative assumption that TERN's activities increase the efficiency of biodiversity protection efforts by 1/1000 (i.e. 0.1%); this is the same assumption as for ALA
C	Total annual benefit (\$M)	2.1	C = A x B

Agricultural productivity

We estimate a conservative and plausible uplift to the value of Australian agriculture as a result of TERN's activities of 0.1%, which is an additional dollar for every \$1,000 of value (Table 4.14). Relevant activities include, for example, research it supports into maximising carbon sequestration in agricultural soil ecosystems⁴⁴ and soil health.⁴⁵

Table 4.14. Calculation: Agricultural productivity–TERN

	Item	Value	Notes
A	GVA of Australian agriculture (\$m)	61,757	2023-24 System of National Accounts, 2023-24
B	Percentage improvement	0.10%	Plausible and conservative assumption, given e.g. https://www.tern.org.au/news/living-soils-in-agriculture/
C	Benefit (\$m)	61.8	C = A x B

Research benefits–time savings

We estimate time saving benefits to researchers from using TERN data in Table 4.15.

⁴⁴ <https://www.tern.org.au/news/flux-research-carbon-sequestration/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.tern.org.au/news/living-soils-in-agriculture/>

Table 4.15. Calculation: Researcher time savings–TERN

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Researchers with interest in TERN data	6,400	Advice from TERN regarding the number of researchers in the field who received TERN Research Directions Survey
B	Percentage using TERN data in any year	10%	Assumption.
C	Time savings due to TERN data or information (hours)	40	We assume that if TERN data and information were not available the research would need to incur at least 1 additional week (40 hours) of time to find the data or substitute data elsewhere (e.g. via a field trip).
D	Value of time (\$/hr) - in paid employment incl. on costs	91.64	Based on the Office of Impact Assessment (2024) default values, updated to account for wage inflation between 2023 and 2025.
E	Total annual benefit (\$M)	2.3	E = A x B x C x D

Cal/Val services

We estimate the annual benefit to the Australian community of the cal/val services provided by TERN as the avoided cost of having one additional satellite. This accounts for TERN giving Australia access to various services from satellites of other countries due to the cal/val services TERN provides. Our assumptions and calculations are presented in Table 4.16.

Table 4.16. Calculation: Benefit of Cal/val services–TERN

	Item	Value	Notes
A	Cost per satellite over 20 years (\$ million)	300	Based on https://www.spaceconnectonline.com.au/industry/5371-budget-australia-will-build-and-operate-four-new-satellites
B	Annuity factor (4.25% discount rate over 20 years)	13.29	The annuity factor is calculated according to the standard formula and allows the calculation of the annual equivalent cost of the satellite.
C	Total annual benefit (\$M)	22.6	C = A / B

Long-tail

Based on the sum of the benefit items calculated above for TERN, and the assumed 25% parameter to estimate long-tail benefits, these benefits are estimated to be \$22.2 million annually.

The economic value of environmental research infrastructure increases non-linearly as long time series data accumulate. Unlike exploratory missions that target specific questions over short timeframes, baseline observing systems like TERN generate measurement records whose value compounds over decades. A single year of ecosystem observations provides a snapshot; thirty years of standardised, continuous measurements reveal trends, enable detection of genuine ecological change against natural variability, and support predictive models that inform policy and land management decisions worth billions of dollars. This temporal depth creates irreplaceable scientific assets, each additional year of observation increases the value of the entire historical record by enabling more robust trend analysis, earlier detection of threshold changes, and validation of climate and ecosystem models. The marginal cost of maintaining continuity (ongoing operations and data management) is modest compared with the cost of recreating lost time series, which is often impossible. Breaking a long-term measurement record does not simply pause value creation: it permanently degrades the analytical power of both past and future observations. This structural characteristic explains why baseline infrastructure like TERN requires institutional commitment spanning decades. Commercial business models, which optimise for revenue certainty over 3 to 7-year horizons, cannot substitute for publicly-funded continuity without deliberate policy mechanisms that guarantee sustained operational funding across political and economic cycles.

Box 4.5.3. Infrastructure synergies

NEESFF research infrastructures routinely combine capabilities to deliver outcomes beyond what any single facility could achieve. A 2024 bushfire early warning system illustrates this dynamic: Geoscience Australia provided satellite data, TERN contributed ground-validated Actual Evapotranspiration measurements, CSIRO supplied hydrological modelling expertise, Bureau of Meteorology provided hourly air temperature and NCI's Gadi supercomputer processed continental-scale datasets. The resulting system provides weekly vegetation stress monitoring across Australia, critical for anticipating catastrophic fire conditions in a warming climate.⁴⁶

Development costs were modest because foundational infrastructure already existed. Replicating this capability independently would require each organisation to build capacities they lack. TERN would need a supercomputer, NCI would need a continental observation network, and Geoscience Australia would need ground validation infrastructure. The infrastructure investment for any one organisation to work alone would be prohibitive while the marginal cost of collaboration across existing NEESFF capabilities was minimal. This demonstrates a key characteristic of coordinated research infrastructure: the benefit-cost ratios calculated for individual organisations likely understate total system value, as they cannot fully capture multiplicative effects when interoperable capabilities combine to address emerging needs.

4.5.3. Costs

We have assumed annual costs of TERN to be approximately \$13.2 million, based on the average actual amount of NCRIS funding granted between July 2013 and June 2028 (in 2025 dollars) to maintain baseline operations of TERN and carry out specific projects.⁴⁷

3.5.4. CBA results

Our indicative CBA results for TERN are presented in Table 4.17. These estimates are based on available information and may significantly understate the overall benefits. Nonetheless they show TERN delivering a very strong RoI, with a benefit-cost ratio of 7.0. This means that for every dollar of costs, \$7.00 in benefits to the community are generated.

⁴⁶ <https://www.tern.org.au/news/satellite-eyes-in-the-sky/> and <https://nci.org.au/research/research-highlights/early-warning-above-how-gadi-detects-vegetation-drought-stress-its>

⁴⁷ <https://www.grants.gov.au/Ga/Show/73883e08-b4b9-43c5-bba1-0aded858906>

Table 4.17. CBA results, annual–TERN

	\$ million
Benefits	
Biodiversity conservation	2.1
Agricultural productivity	61.8
Research benefits (e.g. avoided duplication)	2.3
Cal/Val services	22.6
Long-tail	22.2
<i>Total benefits</i>	<i>111.0</i>
Costs	
Operating costs	13.2
Marginal cost of public funds	2.6
<i>Total costs</i>	<i>15.8</i>
Net benefits	95.1
Benefit-cost ratio	7.0

4.6. Synthesis of CBA findings

Our review of NEESFF facilities and our indicative CBA estimates in these case studies confirm previous findings regarding the high RoI of NEESFF organisations. They are delivering strong net benefits to the Australian community. Using available data and existing studies, we estimate a broad range of benefit-cost ratios, from 3.5 to 15.0.

Given these potential BCRs, and an average BCR across previous studies and these case studies of 6.8 (Table 4.18) and based on estimated total NEESFF annual public funding of \$235 million, **total benefits could exceed \$1.5 billion**. This is likely an underestimate given that some NEESFF organisations obtain significant revenue in addition to Commonwealth funding, and hence total expenditure and hence benefits generated by NEESFF organisations will be higher than this estimate based on total government funding.

Table 4.18. Summary of BCR results for NEESFF organisations

Organisation	Benefit-cost ratio (Central case)	Source
<i>Existing studies</i>		
AAF	8.5	Lateral Economics (2025)
ALA	3.5	Alluvium (2016)
AuScope	15.0	Lateral Economics (2016)
IMOS	4.7	Lateral Economics (2021)
MNF	4.7	RTI International (2020)
<i>New case studies</i>		
ALA	3.8	Case study conducted for this report
APPN	6.7	As above
TERN	7.0	As above
Weighted average across all studies*	6.8	

* Note: The weighted average is calculated by weighting the benefit-cost ratios in Table A by Australian Government funding provided to the organisations since 2017-18. The LE estimated benefit-cost ratio for ALA is used rather than Alluvium's 2016 estimate.

With such a high benefit-cost ratio, we expect a significant fiscal return to taxpayers of investment in NEESFF. Even if only half of the benefits entering into the average BCR of 6.8 contributed to higher GDP, assuming a 30% average tax share of GDP based on ABS data, that would mean \$1.02 of every dollar paid out is returned in taxation revenue. That is, NEESFF may well entirely pay for itself through higher tax revenue, not to mention through the wide range of benefits we have discussed and attempted to quantify in this report.

To a significant extent it is impossible to estimate a benefit-cost ratio for NEESFF organisations as whole, given that we cannot at this stage measure the community's WTP for the non-use existence value of NEESFF-supported research, nor unknown future applications delivering quasi-option value. Even if a WTP survey was conducted, it may be impossible, given the limited time available for people to complete surveys, to explain the full range of NEESFF-supported activities with a view to obtaining an informed and reasonable estimate of WTP.

4. Next steps

The next steps in this project include revising this report following any feedback from NEESFF organisations and supplementing this pilot impact assessment with the following:

- **Standardised data collection instruments and protocols** to support consistent, reliable, and comparable data gathering across NEESFF member organisations.
- **An interactive impact dashboard/scorecard** to summarily (where possible visually) communicate key project findings and support ongoing advocacy and strategic decision-making by NEESFF stakeholders.
 - The dashboard would include a mix of input and output indicators and benefit and cost estimates—e.g. benefit-cost ratio and internal-rate-of-return benefit estimates, and relevant indicators that inform the calculation of benefits (e.g. scientific publications, indicators of research inputs used or data collected, etc.), and capital and operational expenditures.
 - The goal is that the dashboard would show a clear link between NEESFF inputs, activities, outputs and the net benefit estimates.

Appendix A. NEESFF organisations consulted

ACCESS-NRI

AURIN

AuScope

Australian Access Federation (AAF)

Atlas of Living Australia (ALA)

Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN)

Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)

Bioplatforms Australia (BPA)

Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS)

Marine National Facility (MNF)

National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)

National Sea Simulator (SeaSim)

Pawsey

Southern Coastal Research Vessel Fleet (SCRVF)

Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN)

Appendix B. Issues for discussion at interviews

1. Do you have any views on NEESFF facilities that would be good to include in the initial selection of facilities for case studies and quantification of net benefits?
2. Do you have any views on the proposed dashboard/scoreboard? For example:
 - a. Would quarterly or annual updates of the dashboard indicators be useful?
 - b. How would it complement your existing reporting or dashboard?
3. Are there any other methodological frameworks we should be aware of?
4. Do you foresee any challenges in evaluating NEESFF facilities in addition to those in Figure 1?
5. Can you provide LE with historical (at least 5 years) and projected OPEX and CAPEX estimates?
6. What do you consider the significant impacts or benefits of your facility?
 - a. What process do you go through to consider and if possible measure impacts or benefits? Please provide any data you have on this as a result.
 - b. What analysis have you already conducted or commissioned on impacts or benefits?
7. Would there be value in conducting a contingent valuation (CV) study of the existence value of scientific knowledge generated by NEESFF facilities? N.B. We have not included a CV study in the budget. In this pilot assessment, we will attempt to gauge the existence value based on studies of any comparable facilities internationally.
8. Are there any principal users of your facility who would be worthwhile for us to interview to get insights into the benefits to users?

